

Technical Report

Overcoming Challenges of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) & Techno-Economic Assessment (TEA) for Chemical Recycling

*Recommendations for Increasing Transparency,
Comprehensiveness and Comparability of
LCA & TEA for Chemical Recycling Technologies*

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1. Executive Summary

A key building block on the journey towards a net zero society is the recirculation of carbon-containing waste as secondary resources for chemical production. This could potentially contribute to reducing environmental impacts associated with conventional waste treatment (i.e. landfilling and waste incineration) and chemical production (i.e. petrochemistry) processes. Moreover, it could support the transition of such carbon intensive sectors towards circularity and defossilization.

In this context, chemical recycling (CR) is eliciting growing global interest. However, there is considerable controversy about its contribution to a circular and low carbon economy, with concerns ranging from its environmental impacts, resource/energy efficiency, economic competitiveness to challenges for integration in existing supply chains and chemical production infrastructure.

As a tool for the evaluation of environment impacts of a product, process and services throughout its life cycle, life cycle assessment (LCA) is gaining increasing attention as a means to support the evaluation of environmental impacts which are associated with CR technologies compared to conventional waste treatment and chemical production routes. Similarly, techno-economic analysis (TEA) – in providing commercial and market-oriented insights into the economic competitiveness of technology investments – is also gaining interest as a useful tool to support decision processes regarding the investment and deployment of CR technologies.

However, as CR consists of a range of emerging technologies which are in the process of establishing themselves on the market, both LCA and TEA of CR technologies are challenged in their applications in this context. The resulting lack in transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability in both LCA and TEA evaluations – reported for different CR technologies – have thus limited their value in supporting decision processes and socio-political debates about CR's contribution to circularity and defossilization.

To address the challenges of LCA and TEA applications in the CR context, this technical report:

- proposes an integrated reference system to enable a systemic perspective of CR integration in the waste treatment and chemical production value chains to support practitioners in selecting appropriate assessment frameworks for their evaluation;
- highlights aspects specific to CR to be considered in LCA and TEA evaluations;
- develops recommendations for LCA and TEA guidelines to facilitate transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability in their implementation in the CR context;
- presents LCA and TEA checklists to support CR evaluations; and
- demonstrates the application of the developed recommendations on two CR routes i.e. waste pyrolysis and waste gasification.

2. Introduction

The Problem: Challenge of Transparency, Comprehensiveness and Comparability of LCA and TEA Data and Results for Assessment of Environmental & Climate Impacts of Chemical Recycling Technologies

The circular economy is a key pillar of the European Green Deal. However, the challenge of sustainable waste management has reached a new political dimension in recent years. Even though the EU Waste Directive – with the waste hierarchy of reduce, reuse, recycle, recover, landfill – defines a guideline for sustainable waste management, waste remains predominantly landfilled or incinerated. Such disposal routes are associated with significant environmental and climate impacts. Hence, in order to achieve the targets of a circular economy and contribute to achieving a net-zero CO₂-emissions society, it is necessary to achieve higher recycling targets so that materials can be recirculated into the production cycle.

Generally, recycling can be differentiated into mechanical (also referred to as material recycling) and chemical recycling (CR). Mechanical recycling is defined as methods to recycle waste materials into “new” (secondary) raw materials i.e. recyclates without changing the chemical structure of the material. In contrast, CR is used to describe technologies which converts carbon-containing waste chemically into basic chemicals which can then be used as feedstock for the chemical industry. Unlike mechanical recycling, CR changes the chemical structure of the material.

While mechanical recycling is established in certain countries in the EU, it is approaching its limits in meeting higher recycling quotas for carbon-containing waste. Take Germany as an example. It is one of the countries in Europe which has a matured system of waste separation, collection and recycling. However, despite the implementation of higher recycling quotas in its Packaging Law [1], only about 20% of packaging plastics are mechanically recycled as recyclates today. The rest of the packaging materials (i.e. sorting residues) remain combusted in waste incinerators.

Unlike mechanical recycling, CR is currently not widely established on the market. There is significant controversy about its contribution to sustainability and the circular economy. Concerns range from its resource efficiency, environmental impacts, economic competitiveness, to the product integration in existing supply chains and chemical production lines. Its role in the waste hierarchy (e.g. as a potential missing building block between mechanical recycling and waste incineration, definition as chemical recycling OR chemical recovery) is controversially debated. However, as CR consists of diverse emerging technologies which are generally not well documented, decision-makers lack a well-founded data basis to evaluate the potential of CR for a circular carbon economy. Additionally, LCA and

TEA studies on CR technologies are often intransparent as to assumptions and boundary conditions they have utilized for the assessments (i.e. "black box") which limited their comparability.

For LCA evaluations: while applicable methodological guidelines (including ISO standards as well as other general and application specific reference documents) are available, these are not consistently adhered to in past investigations in the CR context. Moreover, the use of LCA for assessing CR technologies has also resulted in specific questions that are not clearly addressed in existing guidelines. These relate especially to LCA assessment scope and interfaces, process variations, waste and product qualities, prospective LCA (i.e. a consideration of CR as an ongoing development process), inventory modelling consistency as well as interpretation and reporting of LCA results.

For TEA evaluations: current applications for CR technologies exhibited a substantial ambiguity in methodological choices and reporting standards. In contrast to LCA where ISO standards are available to guide evaluations, TEA studies for chemical recycling are not conducted according to standardized and proven guidelines. As a result, the application of different numbers and types of indicators generated according to differing methodological principles have led to diverging conclusions and recommendations. Moreover, significant heterogeneity in the reporting focus and structure of TEA reports potentially hinder the traceability and interpretation of study results for the readers.

Motivation & Objectives: In using a systemic and transparent approach, this study

- proposes an integrated reference system to enable a systemic perspective of CR integration in the waste treatment and chemical production value chains to support practitioners in selecting appropriate assessment frameworks for their evaluation;
- highlights aspects specific to CR to be considered in LCA and TEA evaluations;
- develops recommendations for LCA and TEA guidelines to facilitate transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability in their implementation in the CR context;
- presents LCA and TEA checklists to support CR evaluations;
- demonstrates the application of the developed recommendations on 2 CR routes i.e. waste pyrolysis and waste gasification.

Please note that the report does not provide detailed methodological and modelling rules to conduct LCA and TEA investigations or provide quantitative benchmarks. Its goal is to contribute to existing assessment methodologies and guidelines by addressing generalized points of emphasis that are especially relevant in the CR context which are not addressed in reference documentation and/or not uniformly followed in previous investigations of CR processes.

Intended audience: The primary intended audience of the developed recommendations are practitioners who are engaging in technology evaluations to provide quantitative information to support investment and policy/funding decisions as well as R&D activities. The secondary intended audience are recipients of LCA/TEA results who want to comparatively evaluate different CR technologies against each other and also against conventional production routes. The recommendations and checklists in this technical report will support a transparent evaluation process as well as the interpretation of LCA/TEA outcomes and an assessment of their quality and comprehensiveness/weaknesses.

Structure of the report: This report is structured as follows. First, Section 3 introduces the reference system which comprises of conventional plastics production and plastic waste treatment routes as well as alternative CR routes. Following a general overview of LCA and TEA in Section 4, specific aspects for application in the CR context are highlighted and corresponding recommendations for LCA and TEA evaluations are summarized in Sections 5 & 6 respectively. Section 7 presents the checklists which have been developed to support a determination of the transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability of LCA/TEA evaluations which have been carried out for specific CR technologies. Lastly, case studies in Section 8 illustrate the applicability of the developed recommendations and checklists to support LCA & TEA evaluations of CR technologies in the form of waste pyrolysis and waste gasification.

3. Reference system & alternative chemical recycling routes for “Plastics-to-Plastics”

CR is most often understood in a “Plastics-to-Plastics” context, where a recirculation of CR products back into the plastic value chain – similar to conventional plastic recycling – is pursued. Conventional plastic recycling is considered as open-loop recycling, where the recovered product could possibly achieve the original feedstock quality and application, but is predominantly subject of quality decrease and subsequent alternative application options (downcycling). Figure 1 illustrates a schematic reference system in the plastic-to-plastic scope integrating both conventional plastic recycling and CR. It visualizes possible pathways for plastic waste reuse as well as recycling from mechanical recycling to CR in the form of solvent-based purification, depolymerization and feedstock recycling (i.e. liquefaction & gasification), in addition to the respective conventional processes for waste treatment and plastic production that should be considered.

Figure 1: Overview of pathways in plastics recycling [5]

The proposed reference system identifies disintegrated process steps for the integration of CR technologies into existing waste treatment and plastic production pathways. This will support the achievement of a consistent life cycle inventory which is essential to ensure the transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability of LCA and TEA data and results in the CR context. Additionally, the reference system is based on an attributional consideration of the current production situation².

² Note that a more extensive framework to assess the potential impacts of CR application would require a consequential assessment which includes the projected developments in waste treatment and chemical production (e.g. developments in waste sorting, decreasing refinery fuel demand due to electrification of mobility, ...) to identify sustainable current and future integration options for CR technologies.

Chemical recycling: “Waste-to-Chemicals” vs. “Plastics-to-Plastics”

In view of the wide spectrum of waste feedstock which is applicable for CR as well as the range of chemical intermediates and downstream chemical products which are possible, the recommended scope for CR assessment is “*Waste-to-Chemicals*” i.e. beyond the narrow focus on “*Plastics-to-Plastics*”. Reasons being:

- CR does not inherently target to maintain the functionality of the applied waste (plastic) feedstock. Rather, it generally decreases environmental impacts associated with waste treatment and chemical production. A restriction to plastic production is thus not meaningful;
- Even in countries such as Germany with developed source separation system [2–4], a significant portion of plastics remains in mixed/residual waste fractions [6,7]. While plastics may still form the main waste fraction, the applicability and characteristics of mixed/residual waste fractions are predominantly determined by the waste mixture characteristics which can significantly deviate from plastic properties. Therefore, a focus solely on plastic fractions is misleading;
- A predominant focus on plastic products neglects possible target chemicals that are not direct feedstock of major polymers, but which are still associated with significant environmental impacts in the conventional chemical production process (e.g. C4 olefins, methanol, ammonia);
- Note that it remains debatable whether the production of non-carbonaceous chemicals such as ammonia and hydrogen from waste should/can be considered as CR. While such products do not recirculate waste-based carbon into chemical products [8], their production can exhibit similar or even better environmental impacts compared to the production of carbonaceous products. Furthermore, high purity CO₂ can also be recovered during the production process (instead of diluted and dissipated CO₂ as in waste-to-fuel routes) [9]; Their applicability therefore depends on the defined objective of CR application between carbon circularity and quantified sustainability, which do not always go hand in hand [10].
- A focus on plastic products potentially adds unnecessary steps in inventory balancing (e.g. from naphtha to plastics) which complicate and inflate the assessment scope without impacting LCA results.

Figure 2 illustrates the scheme of the proposed reference system for the integration of CR pathways into the conventional waste treatment and plastics (chemical) production value chain.

Figure 2: Scheme of chemical recycling reference system

In the following sections, the reference system for conventional plastics (chemical) production and waste treatment based on best available technique (BAT) will be introduced. Following that, alternative CR technologies and their integration into the value chain will be summarized.

3.1. Conventional plastics production & plastic waste treatment

3.1.1. Pathways and processes for conventional plastics production

Conventional plastics production primarily follows the process steps of refining – steam cracking & processing – polymerization – formulation to processing (see Figure 3) The main process steps for plastics production are briefly introduced below.

- **Refining, steam cracking & processing:** Naphtha – produced from refining of crude oil – is the main intermediate feedstock for plastic production in Europe. While naphtha as a crude oil-based steam cracker feedstock is not regulated strictly and can vary in its properties, it requires specific quality criteria to ensure steam cracker process availability, product yields and quality, thermal efficiency and safe operability [11–14]. Examples for cracker feedstock specifications are shown in Table 1.

Figure 3: Process steps for plastic production

Table 1: Typical quality criteria for naphtha steam cracker feedstock [11,12,15]

Criteria	Limit
Chlorides	<10 wppm
Metals	<1 wppm
Oxygen	<1 wppm
NOx	<2 ppm
oxygenates	<100 ppm
Sulphur	<300 ppm
Olefins	<1 Vol%
Aromatics	<12 Vol%
Paraffins	>65 vol-%
Boiling range	35 – 180 °C

In Europe, naphtha steam cracking is the major source for lower olefins and BTEX aromatics – base chemicals which predominantly deliver the monomers for plastics production. (See Figure 4). Lower olefins are further produced via steam cracking of lighter (e.g. ethane, LPG) and heavier hydrocarbons (e.g. gasoil), and also during catalytic cracking. BTEX aromatic production is heavily associated with crude oil refining. Aromatic-rich pyrolysis gasoline from steam cracking is currently only applied at 30 % for BTEX production, while the rest is used for gasoline production [16]. At the same time, aromatic-rich reformate from naphtha catalytic reforming is primarily used for gasoline production, and also for BTEX recovery.

Figure 4: Production pathways of major plastic types

Plastic monomers are mostly large-scale commodities that are produced and traded globally, which leads to standardized products with ensured specifications. Plastic monomers require high purities (e.g. over 99.9 % for ethylene, benzene, vinyl chloride and DMT; over 99.8% for ethylene glycol; over 99.7% for styrene; over 99.6% for terephthalic acid; over 99.5% for propylene [15]) and contaminant limits to ensure polymerization process performance and plastic quality [17]. Examples for contaminants that are only tolerable in ppm range contents are oxygen, sulfur, hydrogen, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, water and methanol.

- Polymerization [18]:** From monomers, polymers are formed via polymerization. Polyolefins (PE/PP) form the biggest group of polymers, directly synthesized by chain-growth polymerization from ethylene and propylene under varying reaction conditions (temperature, pressure, catalyst, reactor type) to impact the polymer type and properties. Similarly, for PVC and PS, uniform monomers in ethylene-derived vinyl chloride and ethyl benzene-derived styrene are polymerized. Step-growth

polymerization for PET and PUR production requires different bifunctional monomers. PUR plastics are derived from a range of possible compounds, with ethylene oxide and propylene oxide-based polyols, and TDI and MDI (for diisocyanatos) being the primary examples.

In 2019, the total annual European plastics demand was about 50.7 million tonnes, mainly for packaging, building and construction, automotive and electronics [19]. Of these, over 80 % are formed by polyolefins (PE/PP), PVC, PET, PS and PUR (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Distribution of plastic demand in Europe in 2020 [19]

- **Formulation:** Following their production, additives are added to polymers to enhance specific properties or durability. These include [20]:
 - Functional additives (stabilizers, antistatic agents, flame retardants, plasticizers, lubricants, slip agents, curing agents, foaming agents, biocides, etc.),
 - Colorants (pigments, soluble azocolorants, etc.),
 - Fillers (mica, talc, kaolin, clay, calcium carbonate, barium sulphate),
 - Reinforcements (e.g. glass fibres, carbon fibres).

Note that additives can lead to significant issues for recycling processes.

Polymer quality is further described by its technical characteristics (i.e. strength, stiffness, toughness, ductility, impact strength, processability) which influences its applicability [21]:

To conclude, plastics production is significantly associated with the utilization of fossil feedstock and the production of major commodity chemicals. These substances are defined by quality standards and are traded on a global market. Therefore, market

prices are available, as well as environmental footprints of their production. **For harmonization of LCA and TEA in the CR context, the process inventory should thus be targeted to substitute standardized products in the conventional chemical and plastic value chain.**

Reference chemical production process: To define the reference production pathway or mixtures, the BAT documentation by the European Commission can be applied [22–24]. Note that national deviations in supply and production should be considered (e.g. significant fractions of lower olefin production from natural gas liquids in the U.S. and from coal in China) [25,26].

3.1.2. Pathways and processes for conventional plastic waste treatment

Waste treatment is – in terms of composition, source separation, preprocessing and final treatment of waste fractions – generally significantly more diverse within the EU compared to chemical production. Therefore, **waste treatment processes have to be balanced individually with respect to the specific framework when included in chemical recycling assessments.** The most significant processing technologies for plastic-containing waste fractions include mechanical recovery, mechanical biological treatment and waste incineration.

Plastic waste can be found in different types of waste streams & qualities (see Figure 6 for an example of plastic-containing waste streams in Germany).

Figure 6: Plastic-containing waste streams (Example Germany)

Conventional plastic waste treatment goes through multiple pathways (see Figure 7). Ideally, for production & processing (pre-consumer) of plastic residues as well as source-separated (post-consumer) plastic-rich waste fractions, mechanical sorting will enable the extraction of

sorted plastics which – following processing and regranulation into recyclates – can be channeled back as recycled intermediate feedstock into the polymer production process. In contrast, plastic fractions in (post-consumer) residual MSW are either directly incinerated, or goes through mechanical (-biological or -physical) treatment to produce refuse-derived fuel (RDF) which is then incinerated, or used to substitute fossil fuel for production (e.g. for cement production). In the following section, the main process steps for waste treatment will be briefly summarized.

Figure 7: Process steps for waste treatment

- Mechanical sorting for recycling [27–29]:** Material recovery (MR) is the primary treatment option for light weight packaging and other plastic-rich waste fractions. The primary target of the process is the recovery of plastic and non-plastic materials with high purity for direct recycling. Material sorting units are composed of a range of single sorting and processing steps, including sieving, density separation, optical separation by near-infrared sensors and manual sorting and quality control (see Figure 8). The recovery rate and quality of the recovered plastic fractions and polymer type vary depending on the applied technology. Non-recoverable fractions are collected as mixed plastic waste (MPW) and sorting residue fractions (SR), which are subsequently thermally treated via conventional processes. BAT documentation is available [30], further essential process data for MR including benchmark recovery efficiencies and substitution ratios can be derived from other sources [27,31,32], but are subject of ongoing research [21,28,33].

Figure 8: Process steps for material recovery

- Mechanical (biological or physical treatment) [34–36]:** Mechanical biological treatment (MBT) includes a range of process configurations for pretreatment of municipal waste and other waste fractions [37]. Primary target is the generation of a high-calorific fraction by mechanical sorting. The biological treatment of the remaining organic-rich fraction by anaerobic digestion enables the generation of biogas, which can be used thermally to generate electricity and heat in a combined heat and power unit (CHP). Alternatively, the organic fraction can be composted for biological drying and conversion of biogenic carbon, in order to generate a residue that is suitable for landfilling [38] (see Figure 9).

An alternative to MBT is mechanical physical treatment (MPT). The main difference to MBT is – instead of biological treatment – a physical treatment of remaining organic-rich fraction (e.g. via natural-gas fired drying).

BAT documentation for mechanical, biological and physical treatment processes is available [30].

Figure 9: Process steps for mechanical-biological treatment

- **Waste incineration:** Waste incineration aims to process combustible waste compounds by oxidation and consequent flue gas treatment, with possible energy recovery in form of electricity and heat, and recovery of value products from solid residues (ash/slag) (see Figure 10). The waste-to-energy efficiency of waste incineration can vary significantly depending on applied equipment, process configuration and feedstock [39]. ***Benchmarks for energy and material recovery as well as emission reduction measures for waste incineration are summarized in BAT documentation [40] and should be considered during process balancing.***

Figure 10: Process steps for waste incineration

Reference waste treatment process: Currently, there is no consistent best practice definition available to determine the reference waste treatment process for specific waste origins and compositions. An orientation is provided by the waste hierarchy defined in the EU Waste Framework Directive, which prioritizes prevention and preparation for re-use before recycling, (thermal) recovery and disposal [41]. Landfilling – as a disposal technology – should not be considered as a reference waste treatment process as thermal recovery via incineration is a widely applicable alternative for the treatment of carbon-containing waste. Furthermore, if the conventional reference is unclear (e.g. for post-production/pre-consumer residues or for mixed polyolefin fractions from mechanical sorting), both recycling and incineration should be considered.

3.2. Chemical recycling technologies

A number of publications provide general technological classifications and categorizations of associated definitions for CR [5,42,43]. ***The present investigation focuses on relevant aspects for balancing of CR processes and pathways for LCA and TEA. The classification is therefore related to the waste stream input and applicable plastic precursor output.*** Below, an overview of individual process steps and potentially relevant balancing aspects is provided.

CR processes can be generally classified into 4 categories namely (1) liquefaction, (2) gasification, (3) depolymerization, and (4) solvent-based purification (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Process steps for chemical recycling

- Liquefaction includes all processes that primarily produce a liquid hydrocarbon mixture, that is further processed (internally or externally) to steam cracker feedstock and/or for the recovery of BTEX aromatics from a mixture.
- Gasification covers all processes that primarily produce a syngas with CO and H₂ as the main components, which is subsequently converted downstream to a plastic predecessor by chemical synthesis.

Gasification and liquefaction can be collectively summarized as feedstock recycling technologies due to their production of intermediates in early stages of the plastics production chain.

- Depolymerization includes all processes in which specific plastic monomers or chemical intermediates are directly recovered.
- Solvent-based purification includes processes to directly recover polymers with high purity for direct reintegration in plastics processing without a polymerization step.

The labeling of solvent-based purification as CR is debatable as they are frequently considered as advanced mechanical recycling technologies. Nevertheless, they are included in this investigation as they are often included in comparative assessments with CR technologies.

A differentiation between chemical and non-chemical applications of CR technologies is not always directly possible based on the conversion technology itself (e.g. pyrolysis). However, when assessed as a CR technology, the products should address the substitution of chemical intermediates that are produced as large-scale primary products (i.e. no minor side products in co-production processes). Addressed products that should be avoided in the CR context include crude oil, fuel oil and other fuel fractions. Further, CR processes should be differentiated from Power-to-X application.

3.2.1. Liquefaction-based chemical recycling

Figure 12 illustrates the main process steps for liquefaction.

Figure 12: Process steps for liquefaction-based chemical recycling

Feedstock [29,44–46]: Liquefaction technologies vary in their applicable plastic-containing waste type. Relevant parameters are the fractions of standard packaging polymers (esp. PE, PP), other plastic fractions (esp. PET, PVC), non-plastic combustible fractions (esp. organics) and inert fractions (esp. metals). Non-plastic fractions are undesirable for technologies that employ extruders for feedstock preconditioning and feeding. Non-standard packaging plastic fractions can cause operation issue (e.g. PET can lead to clogging by crystallization, PVC to corrosion). Applicable waste type and composition need to be considered during feedstock selection, presorting and/or preconditioning (e.g. dichlorination).

Liquefaction pathways variations and characterization: Liquefaction-based CR includes process pathways for the production of a liquid hydrocarbon mixture directly from the applied waste fraction. This liquid hydrocarbon mixture is applied to replace cracking feedstock or cracking product fractions (i.e. feedstock recycling). Liquefaction-based CR processes include pyrolysis, catalytic cracking, hydrocracking and catalytic reforming processes. Depending on the process technology, a combination of process steps can be applied for primary waste

conversion and secondary liquid processing. E.g. hydrocracking can be applied directly for plastic waste conversion or for pyrolysis oil upgrading.

Liquefaction process [43,44,46–48]: Liquefaction is generally an endothermic process with the objective to produce a liquid hydrocarbon mixture (pyrolysis oil). Further possible products include pyrolysis gas, solid residue and an aquatic phase.

- ***Energy supply*** – Liquefaction processes can be heated by electrical heating, direct fired heating of internal (side products) and/or external fuels or indirect heating via heat carrier material. Further, low-temperature liquefaction processes can employ friction heat from internal instruments for heat generation. The total heat demand consists of the required heat for feedstock heating and the liquefaction process reaction enthalpy. Quantitatively, the net process heat demand is predominantly determined by the feedstock heating, while the reaction heat is less significant and can even be negative for non-plastic fractions [49–52]. Heating-associated fuel demand and flue gas emissions (fuel-based and combustion-based) should be considered during process balancing. Direct hydrocracking/hydropyrolysis-based processes can be net exothermic without external heat demand, but hydrogen demand should be considered in this case [29,53].
- ***Utility material application*** – Liquefaction technologies vary in catalyst application necessity. Catalytic processes are generally characterized by lower reaction temperature and higher liquid product yield, but catalyst supply needs to be considered in balancing. Also, spent catalyst accumulates in solid residue fractions, where the catalyst is either recovered or post-treated. Other possibly applied solid process additives include neutralization agents, e.g. limestone. Furthermore, liquefaction processes frequently apply starting oils, which should be considered in process balancing if they cannot be substituted with product oil during long-term continuous operation [54].

Residue treatment: Depending on liquefaction technology, applied feedstock and additives, solid residue with varying yield and composition will be generated and its treatment should be considered. Compared to residues from gasification processes (see below), liquefaction residues (also referred to as char or coke) generally have a higher remaining carbon content and heating value. Treatment options include thermal treatment with or without energy recovery (associated with significant incineration emissions) or substitution of fossil fuels if applicable (e.g. for cement kilns).

Pyrolysis oil characterization, processing, feedstock substitution [12,55,56]: Primary product oil from liquefaction processes varies widely in its properties. This affects its applicability and upgrading demand. Characteristics include:

- High contents of unsaturated hydrocarbons (especially aromatics (mono and poly aromatics), olefins, naphthenes),
- Wide boiling range (up to approximately 400 °C),
- Low hydrogen-carbon ratio,
- High contents of hetero atoms (especially oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur, chlorine, metals) depending on applied feedstock and pretreatment,
- Low heating value (compared to saturated hydrocarbons).

In view of naphtha quality requirements, primary liquefaction oil is generally not applicable directly as steam cracker feedstock. Objectives for oil upgrading are the removal of hetero atoms, hydrocarbon saturation and ring opening and boiling range adjustment to achieve steam cracker specifications. Upgrading process steps include deoxygenation, hydrotreating and hydrocracking (which can be combined depending on upgrading technology), and product fractionation. Significant balancing elements include demands of hydrogen, electricity and heat for fractionation (from fuel gas or external sources), emissions from fuel gas and off-gas combustion, and yields of byproducts (fuel gas, LPG, liquid hydrocarbon fractions).

Literature of upgrading inventories to steam cracker feedstock is limited. It differs from conventional heavy residue or bio crude upgrading mainly in the addressed product (i.e. naphtha equivalent) which requires significant aromatic saturation and hydrocracking of middle distillate fraction. This is conventionally avoided when fuels are produced. Nevertheless, the technology is commercially advertised (e.g. PureStep™ technology by Haldor Topsoe, Rewind® Mix by Axens [57–59]). Upgrading process inventories (including e.g. hydrogen demand) are specific to the pyrolysis oil composition, which is in turn dependent on the applied waste feedstock and liquefaction technology. They therefore cannot be applied directly from other application data without adaptation.

Besides a substitute for naphtha, liquefaction products can also be upgraded to replace conventional feedstock fractions for BTX aromatic recovery. The main conventional fractions for BTX recovery are pyrolysis gasoline from naphtha cracking and reformate from naphtha catalytic reforming [60]. Compared to upgrading for naphtha, hydroprocessing is less severe and hydrogen demand is lower. BTX yield of upgraded liquefaction product is generally lower than for conventional BTX feedstock (BTX content over 60 % [61]). Hence, product yield differences should be considered during balancing, or catalytic reforming to increase BTX yield.

If the main targeted application of liquefaction product is the substitution of crude oil as general refinery feedstock, the main consequential products are conventional liquid fuels in a conventional refinery setting. This should not be considered a viable CR pathway, unless a process reference including refinery balance is provided and included during inventory balancing for the predominant production of chemical feedstock instead of liquid fuels (oil-to-chemicals [62,63]).

3.2.2. Gasification-based chemical recycling

Figure 13 illustrates the main process steps for gasification.

Figure 13: Process steps for gasification-based chemical recycling

The following aspects should be considered for gasification-based CR:

Feedstock and pretreatment [46,64,65]: Waste gasification can be applied to a wide range of feedstock. Besides plastic and non-plastic fractions, it is also applicable for mixed and residual waste. Depending on the gasification technology, required feedstock characteristics will vary. These generally include a range of physical (e.g. particle size and density), fuel (e.g. heating value, water, ash, fixed carbon and volatile content, ash melting point) and compositional conditions (e.g. chlorine content). Gasification process performance (i.e. carbon conversion, syngas yield and composition) are significantly impacted by feedstock characteristics. Hence, a direct adaptation of process inventories between different feedstock is not applicable/meaningful.

The necessity of pretreatment steps before gasification depends on the applied waste type and the gas solid contacting regime in the gasification reactor. Gasification is conducted generally either in fixed-bed, fluidized-bed, entrained-flow or a combination of these.

- *Fixed-bed gasification* requires large and compacted feed particles (cm range). Applied feedstock thus require pelletizing which is associated with electricity demand.
- *Fluidized bed gasification* requires feedstock in mm range. This means that shredding can be required.

- *Entrained-flow gasification* requires μm range-sized particles or liquid feedstock. Unconditioned waste fractions (especially soft plastics) are not grindable and are thus not suitable for this type of gasification process. However, certain waste fractions can be pretreated thermally via pyrolysis (or torrefaction) to generate a grindable coke. For thermal pretreatment, heat supply has to be considered (see liquefaction processes above), as well as electricity demand for coke grinding.

Gasification process & heat supply [46–48,66–68]: The gasification process can either be autothermal or allothermal, or a combination of both.

- *Autothermal gasification* – reaction heat is generated via partial oxidation with oxygen as a gasification agent. Oxygen is supplied in significant purity (at least 90 vol-%) and can be generated by cryogenic, adsorption or membrane-based air separation or obtained from external sources. Note that air-blown gasification – in contrast to oxygen-blown gasification – is suitable for producing a raw gas for thermal utilization (i.e. air-blown gasification as an advanced waste-to-energy technology [69]). This raw gas is not viable for chemical utilization due to the nitrogen dilution of the produced syngas.
- *Allothermal gasification:* reaction heat is supplied by external sources. These can either be heated surfaces within the gasification reactor or by heat carrier material (e.g. metallic or mineral bodies) that are periodically reheated in an external reaction chamber. The reaction heat can be generated by electric heating (e.g. via plasma torches) with a significant electricity demand that is to be considered. It can also be generated via combustion of either externally supplied fuel gas, fractions of the generated gas and/or side products of the gasification process or subsequent syngas processing steps (e.g. coke, waste gases). The corresponding fuel demand and resulting combustion emissions are to be considered in the process inventory.

After the primary gasification step for the major solid conversion, a secondary post gasification step is possibly applied for further carbon and hydrocarbon conversion as well as to increase raw gas temperature to improve gas quality (especially to achieve lower methane and tar yield).

Besides oxygen, the supply of required gasification agents in steam and/or CO_2 has to be considered. Process steam can be supplied by energy integration along the syngas process chain and/or by additional heating. Steam parameters have to be considered especially for high-pressure gasification. Also, additional utility materials for gasification have to be taken in consideration, e.g. limestone as fluxing agent.

Syngas characterization: The composition of the product gas (i.e. syngas) from gasification processes varies widely depending on feedstock and gasification conditions (heat supply,

temperature/pressure, gas solid contacting regime). Syngas composition significantly affects the requirements for syngas purification and conditioning, its applicability and the resulting product yield for chemical production. This is why syngas should not be considered a uniform allocable product and should only be assessed in context with its direct application. Major syngas characteristics include:

- syngas yield (H_2 and CO); H_2 - CO ratio; CO_2 content
- inert contaminants: CH_4 , N_2
- Corrosive contaminants: chlorine-based (e.g. HCl), Sulphur-based (e.g. H_2S), nitrogen-based (e.g. NH_3 , HCN)
- tar, oil

Solid residue characterization and treatment [64,65,70]: Extraction of non-convertible, inert waste fractions are an essential technological focus of gasification processes. Inert materials are predominantly extracted as bottom product in form of ash or slag, but also as fly ash from downstream gas purification processes. Major characteristics of solid residues are the remaining contents of carbon, hydrocarbon components and heavy metals as well as their leachability (Note: slag generally has a lower remaining carbon content and is less leachable compared to ash). Depending on the solid residue characteristics and the country-specific regulations for landfilling and/or further utilization, post-treatment can be required (e.g. post-combustion) and should be considered during the assessment.

Syngas processing [71–76]: A generalized scheme of waste gasification-based processes for chemical production is shown in Figure 14. Similar to gasification processes, there is a significant variance between the characteristics of specific process technologies for syngas purification, syngas-based synthesis and product upgrading. Some general aspects that should be considered during inventory generation are listed below.

Figure 14: Generalized process flowsheet of gasification-based chemical recycling [47]

Table 2 summarizes the necessary syngas characteristics and purities that are typically required for syngas-based downstream synthesis processes. Further sensitive syngas contaminants that require high-purity removal include NH₃, HCN and hydrogen halides.

Table 2: Overview of syngas characteristic requirements for chemical synthesis [71]

Criteria	Methanol synthesis	Fischer-Tropsch synthesis	Ammonia synthesis
Syngas composition	$\frac{H_2 - CO_2}{CO + CO_2} = 2$	$\frac{H_2}{CO} = 2$	$\frac{H_2}{N_2} = 3$
CO ₂	compatible	compatible	<10 ppmv
CH ₄ + Ar + N ₂	<4 vol-%	<5 vol-%	<0.4 vol-% (N ₂ excl.)
Sulphur, chlorine comp	<0,1 mg/m ³	<0,1 mg/m ³	<<1 mg/m ³
Alkali comp	<0,2 mg/m ³	<10 ppb	-

Primary syngas scrubbing targets syngas cooling and the removal of dust, tars and oils and water-soluble components, especially NH₃ and HCl. Significant inventory balancing elements include the demand for fresh water, cooling water and neutralizing agent, and the generation of waste water quantities. Depending on the syngas composition (especially corrosive component content), dry primary gas treatment can be applied based on physical filtration, adsorption and catalytic tar cracking. For dry gas treatment, especially the adsorber material supply and treatment need to be considered.

In the CO shift step, the syngas composition (esp. CO-H₂ ratio) is adjusted in one or more catalytic reactors, according to the reaction:

The further away the raw gas CO-H₂ ratio is from the desired value for the downstream product synthesis, the more process-based CO₂ is necessarily formed in the process. Considerable balancing elements are the balance of required (for syngas saturation) and produced steam (from heat recovery), cooling water demand and the produced CO₂ fraction in the syngas. Application of CO shift can be reduced or voided by integration of hydrogen from external sources. This however has to be considered in the assessment.

Following gas purification consists of acid gas removal and sulfur recovery. In an acid gas removal unit, contaminant gas components are removed from syngas, primarily CO₂ and H₂S, but also traces of NH₃, other sulfur components, higher hydrocarbons (naphtha fraction) and water. Large-scale applications employ physical (e.g. methanol as absorbent) or chemical (e.g. amine-based absorbent) absorption processes. Depending on process configuration and applied absorbent, the process can either be selective (separate generation of a high-purity CO₂ stream and a high-yield H₂S stream) or non-selective (one off-gas stream). Major

balancing elements include primarily low-temperature heat (for absorbent regeneration) and electricity demand, further cooling water demand, absorbent makeup and waste water generation. Sulfur recovery can be performed by catalytic (Claus-type), biological or selective-oxidation processes to recover elementary sulfur. Major characteristics include sulfur recovery, tail-gas purity and tail-gas post-treatment.

Thermal processing (incineration) of generated off-gases from various process steps should be considered. Characteristic parameters include fuel gas-specific emissions (CO₂, sulfur dioxide, fuel-based NO_x, chloride), combustion-specific emissions (thermal NO_x, CO) and efficiency of energy recovery (if considered in the plant configuration).

Syngas utilization [75,77–82]: Syngas offers a wide array of potential chemical utilizations (see Figure 15). Two potential pathways for syngas integration in plastics production pathways are exemplarily considered in this report namely (1) a methanol-based pathway for olefin substitution, and (2) a Fischer Tropsch (FT)-based pathway for naphtha substitution. Other process pathways ranging from substitution of natural gas-based chemicals in hydrogen, ammonia and methanol to alternative technologies in methanol-to-aromatics, direct olefin synthesis, ethanol-to-ethylene and Fischer-Tropsch-to-olefins are also possible.

Figure 15: Overview of syngas utilization pathways [47]

- **Methanol pathway for olefin substitution** – Methanol synthesis from syngas is a standard large-scale chemical process, employing a catalytic reactor with limited once-through conversion and gas recycle. Factors to consider in balancing are electricity (for

compression), steam production (from heat recovery), cooling water and produced purge gas. Methanol is subsequently separated by staged distillation from co-produced light product gases, fuel oils and water. Demand of low-temperature heat and cooling water, generated tail-gas and waste water should be considered.

Methanol is a globally traded commodity chemical with regulated quality standards and available reference data for production prices and environmental footprints. Methanol is also a precursor in plastics production (e.g. for MDI production). However, current methanol utilization in plastics production is limited. Hence, to enable large-scale substitution of plastic precursors, it is necessary to consider further conversion to monomers e.g. lower olefins.

Methanol-to-olefin (MTO) synthesis is mature technology which is applied economically in coal-based chemical plants especially in China. The process is catalytic with a high conversion rate (i.e. without methanol recycling) to produce an olefinic product mixture (i.e. predominantly ethylene and propylene). Characteristic factors include steam balancing (demand for feed mixing, production from heat recovery), and combustion emissions from catalyst regeneration (coke burn off). Olefin separation and purification is performed similar to steam cracking plants, with a difference in product composition (i.e. less production of hydrogen and aromatic compounds). For balancing, heat and electricity demand, caustic scrubbing agent demand and co-produced side products (fuel gas, LPG and higher olefins) should be considered.

Fischer Tropsch pathway for naphtha substitution – Fischer Tropsch (FT) synthesis is globally applied in large-scale gas-to-liquids and coal-to-liquids applications, primarily for the production of liquid fuels. Paraffinic naphtha is conventionally not the primary product, so balancing of conventional plants with high yields in fuels is not desirable for investigations on CR. However, the resulting product distribution can be adjusted during the product upgrading to achieve high yields of naphtha. Paraffinic naphtha from FT synthesis has a lower content of naphthenic and aromatic compounds compared to fossil naphtha. This leads to performance improvements during steam cracking (esp. olefin yields) [83,84] which should be considered in inventory balancing.

FT synthesis is a catalytic process with recycle of unreacted syngas to produce a primarily paraffinic hydrocarbon mix (syncrude). Depending on catalyst and reactor technology, the syncrude varies in composition (fractions of olefinic, aromatic and oxygenate compounds) and its boiling range. Major characteristics include electricity demand and steam production. Depending on the process configuration, formed gaseous hydrocarbons can be reformed and recycled to the reactor to increase product

yield. Possible additional process units include autothermal reformer (oxygen required), steam reformer (flue gas emissions generated) and CO₂ scrubber (CO₂ emission and absorbent makeup).

FT upgrading consists of hydrotreatment, hydrocracking, product fractionation and tail-gas treatment. Hydrogen is required during hydrotreating (i.e. saturation of non-paraffinic compounds, removal of oxygenates) and hydrocracking (i.e. cracking of long hydrocarbon chains), but can also be recovered from FT recycle gas and tail-gas. Hence, hydrogen balancing depends on the specific system configuration. Further characteristics for process balancing include electricity and cooling water demand, fuel gas demand and flue gas emissions (for fractionation heating demand), and yields of co-produced fuel gas and LPG.

3.2.3. Depolymerization-based chemical recycling

The objective of depolymerization technologies (see Figure 16) is the direct recovery of monomers as feedstock for conventional polymerization of virgin-grade polymers. Depolymerization can be conducted chemically (solvolysis or chemolysis; with application of solvent and/or catalyst) or thermally (pyrolysis) depending on the applied technology. Furthermore, processes can be differentiated between selective and non-selective.

Figure 16: Process steps for depolymerization-based chemical recycling

Feedstock and pretreatment [85,86]: Depolymerization technologies are primarily applicable for condensation and addition polymers, especially PET, PU and PA, as well as for PS. Depolymerization is generally applied for manufacturing residues or sorted waste streams of high purity. If not integrated in the feedstock supply, mechanical pretreatment (shredding) should be considered. EPS (expanded PS) requires melting or compacting before feeding. Also, polyolefinic or mixed plastic feeds can be applied in non-selective depolymerization with pretreatment demands similar to liquefaction processes.

Depolymerization process variations and characterization [85–92]:

- **Solvolysis** – Depending on solvent, solvolysis processes are considered glycolysis, alcoholysis, aminolysis, methanolysis or hydrolysis. The recovered product and the

resulting application vary between solvents [29]. Besides solvent supply, solvolysis processes can apply solid catalysts and alkaline solutions, which should be considered during balancing. Solvolysis is conducted at low to moderate temperature. Separation and recovery processes include crystallization, filtration and vaporization and distillation processes with a specific configuration depending on the applied solvent and process technology. Major characteristics include product yield, solvent recovery, heat supply and temperature level for the solvolysis process and regeneration, electricity supply for pressurization and mechanical treatment, and post-treatment of solid residues and spent solvent.

- **Thermal depolymerization** – This is characterized by higher temperatures and energy demand supplied by either electrical heating or fired heaters (associated with fuel demand and flue gas-based emissions), but solvents and catalysts are avoided (supply and recovery demand). Monomer product selectivity is generally lower in the produced oil. Monomer recovery and purification (i.e. close boiling range, high purity demand) can be associated with significant energy and equipment demand and should be considered in the assessment. Formed gas fractions can be integrated for fuel gas supply.
- Non-selective depolymerization – The category includes processes that aim to directly generate target monomers or chemical intermediates without secondary conversion steps, but in hydrocarbon mixtures with lower individual component yields. Waste conversion resembles pyrolysis or gasification processes with focus on the respective balancing aspects (including process energy supply, side product treatment, product gas contaminant removal). Hydrocarbon gas separation, product purification and treatment or utilization of non-chemical product fractions need to be considered during inventory balancing.

3.2.4. Solvent-based purification

The objective for solvent-based purification technologies is the recovery of high-purity polymers without breaking them down on monomer level (see Figure 17). More specifically, it targets the removal of additives and the selective separation of one polymer type from other plastics. Since it's primarily a physical solution process instead of a chemical process, the declaration as chemical recycling is debatable. As the process assessment framework is similarly unclear to feedstock recycling, solvent-based chemical recycling is also considered in this study.

Figure 17: Process steps for solvent-based chemical recycling

Feedstock [93,94]: Solvent-based purification is applicable for plastic mixtures or pre-sorted mono fractions or plastic manufacturing residues. Fractions with high content of the targeted plastic type are preferred. Non-plastic fractions are not desirable. If necessary, applied plastic fractions are preconditioned (shredding, washing drying) and the required energy demand needs to be considered.

Extraction process technology [93,94]: Generally, the feedstock is contacted with a selective solvent at elevated temperature and low to moderate pressure, dissolving the target fraction in the solvent. Depending on technology, energy can be introduced to the solution process by external heating or alternative sources (i.e. microwave, ultrasound) due to the moderate process conditions. Solvent is separated from the insoluble residue by filtration. The target polymer is recovered from the solvent either by solvent vaporization or (predominantly) addition of a non-solvent and reprecipitation and consequential filtration. The solvent/non-solvent mixture and co-solved additives can be separated by distillation. Relevant criteria for evaluation include energy/heat demand, pressure and temperature level for extraction and recovery, recovery yields of target polymer and additives, and solvent and non-solvent loss and makeup demand. Furthermore, treatment of insoluble residue should be considered.

Recovered polymer characterization [94]: The quality of the recovered polymer is critical for the assessment of solvent-based extraction processes. Quality should be evaluated in terms of the presence of low-molecular weight impurities (solvent residues, additives, and degradation products). Furthermore, polymer quality should be considered since polymer chains are to be maintained in the process (i.e. composition pattern; chemical, morphological, mechanical and rheological properties; associated with polymer functionality).

CR products include base chemicals for material production as well as feedstock for chemical production. An overview of potential intermediates and products from CR which can be used for organic chemical production is illustrated in Figure 18 below. While a distinction should be made between CR products from those associated with waste-to-energy and waste-to-fuel pathways, this is challenging due to structural interconnection of chemical feedstock and fuel production in the refinery context. The following criteria for CR products are therefore proposed:

- The addressed CR product is a product/intermediate in the chemical production value chain,
- the quantitative demand for chemical production warrants a large-scale CR production in the targeted scale,
- the addressed product should currently be primarily applied for chemical production (i.e. no substitution of crude oil, refinery fuel products, SNG/fuel gas and coal), and
- no substitution of associated refinery low value or waste products that are currently applied for chemical production, including heavy distillation residues and petcoke.

Figure 18: Simplified flowchart of organic chemical production [95,96]

4. General overview of LCA & TEA

4.1. LCA

4.1.1. LCA methodology guidelines

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a methodology for the structured evaluation of direct and indirect environmental impacts of products, processes or services throughout its life cycle. With growing global attention on sustainability, defossilization and circularity, LCA is increasingly being utilized to support evaluation and decision processes regarding the opportunities and risks of products/technologies/services.

The process of conducting an LCA and its structural elements are standardized in ISO 14044 and 14044 [9,97]. According to the ISO, the LCA process is structured into four phases:

- goal and scope definition,
- life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis,
- life cycle impact assessment (LCIA),
- interpretation.

Phase 1 – Goal & scope definition: The goal definition should include all relevant information on the reason for carrying out the study, the intended audience and further utilization of the results. The scope of the study includes all methodological assumptions and conditions that are applied for conducting the study to ensure transparency, comparability and conclusiveness of the study and its results. Focus points include the definition of the assessed system (i.e. system boundaries, functional unit), sources and requirements of the applied data, methodological conditions (i.e. applied allocation rules and impact categories) and limitations of the assessment.

Phase 2 – Life cycle inventory analysis (LCI): In this phase, required data is collected and interconnected, in order to quantify associated energy and material streams within the system (intermediate flows) and streams extracted from or emitted to the environment (elementary flows). The involved processes are divided into a foreground system and a background system. The foreground system involves the processes that are specific to the production system and that are affected by decisions within. Foreground processes are mostly the focus of individual modelling and balancing. The background system includes the processes that are not specific to the production system, that are included in numerous production systems and that are not significantly affected by its changes (e.g. electricity supply). Background processes are usually not modelled in detail but applied from averaged supply data, for example from LCI databases [98]. Figure 19 illustrates the schematic structure of a life-cycle inventory model.

Figure 19: Schematic structure of life cycle inventory model (adapted from [98])

Phase 3 – Life cycle impact analysis (LCIA): In the LCIA phase, the environmental impact of the investigated system is quantified with regards to specific environmental impact categories, that can include global warming, fossil resource depletion, acidification and others. The determined elementary flows are multiplied with individual characterization factors for specific chemical components or component groups in each impact category. The total impact in each category is determined by the sum of all individual impacts of the elementary flows. Conclusive sets of characterization factors are available in form of characterization models (e.g. IPCC characterization factors for the impact concerning climate change [99]). Furthermore, sets of complementary characterization models in various impact categories are summarized and maintained in characterization methodologies (e.g. Product Environmental Footprint PEF, CML 2001 and ReCiPe 2016) [100].

Phase 4 – Interpretation phase: Finally, in the interpretation phase, the acquired results are evaluated in perspective of the defined goals of the investigation and recommendations may be derived. The interpretation further considers the robustness and uncertainty of the results, sensitivity of key parameters and limitations of the applicability of the results.

While the ISO standards mentioned provide a structural orientation to the process of conducting an LCA, they are not specific enough to give a methodical guideline [101]. More extensive and detailed guideline documents are available to specify possible approaches on how to conduct LCAs.

For guidelines on how to conduct LCA in general, please refer to:

- European Commission. 2010. International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) handbook: Review schemes for Life Cycle Assessment, Publications Office, Luxembourg. Available under: <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/uploads/ILCD-Handbook-Review-schemes-LCA-online-March2010-ISBN-fin-v1.0-EN.pdf>
- Sonnemann, G., Vigon, B. 2011. Global Guidance Principles for Life Cycle Assessment Databases: A Basis for Greener Processes and Products, United Nations Environment Programme. Available under: <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2011%20-%20Global%20Guidance%20Principles.pdf>

For specific applications of LCA in waste treatment and chemical production:

- Manfredi, S., Pant, R. 2011. Supporting Environmentally Sound Decisions for Waste Management: A technical guide to Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for waste experts and LCA practitioners, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. Available under: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC65850>
- Laurent, A., Clavreul, J., Bernstad, A., Bakas, I., Niero, M., Gentil, E., Christensen, T.H., Hauschild, M.Z. 2013. Review of LCA studies of solid waste management systems – Part II: Methodological guidance for a better practice, Waste Management 34: 589–606. Available under: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2013.12.004>
- Tonini, D., Garcia-Gutierrez, P., and Nessi, S., Environmental effects of plastic waste recycling, EUR 30668 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-34297-7, doi:10.2760/955772, JRC122455
- Nessi, S., Sinkko, T., Bulgheroni, C., Garcia-Gutierrez, P., Giuntoli, J., Konti, A., Sanye Mengual, E., Tonini, D., Pant, R., Marelli, L. and Ardente, F., Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of alternative feedstocks for plastics production, EUR 30725 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-38144-0, doi:10.2760/693062, JRC125046

Generally, **to increase comparability of LCA assessments, the product environmental footprint methodology proposed by the European Commission [102] should be applied. Critical elements include the specification of applicable impact assessment methodologies and the application of system expansion and the circular footprint formula for End-of-Life consideration.**

4.1.2. Overview of LCA Studies for CR Technologies

Table 3 and Table 4 provide an overview of LCA investigations in the CR context.

Table 3: Overview of LCA investigations on CR technologies (Part 1)

Source	Year	Scope	Waste fraction	Process	Process data source	Main product substitution	Reference waste treatment
[103]	2003	WP	EoL vehicle parts	Gasification	Literature	Methanol	MR, INC, LF
[104]	2003	WP	Mixed PVC	Solvent-based purification.	Modelling	PVC	INC, LF
[105]	2005	WP	PE, PET	Hydrocracking Pyrolysis	Literature	Crude oil; Atm. residue; naphtha; LPG	MR, INC, LF
[106]	2008	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Literature	Paraffins, naphtha, diesel	MR, INC, LF
[107]	2010	WP	PET	Solvent-based purification.	Literature	PET	MR
[108]	2012	WP	PVC, PET	Solvent-based purification.	Modelling	PVC, PET	INC
[109]	2013	PP	RDF (MSW)	Gasification	Literature	Ethylene	MR, INC
[110]	2014	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Literature	Atm. residue; naphtha; LPG	MR
[111]	2014	WP	RDF (MSW)	Gasification	Literature	Liquid fuels	
[112]	2015	WP	MSW	Pyrolysis	Literature	Diesel, gasoline	INC, LF
[113]	2017	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Literature	Diesel, naphtha	INC, LF
[114]	2018	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Industry	Wax, naphtha, crude oil, fuel oil	INC, LF
[115]	2019	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	unclear	Crude oil	MR
[116]	2019	WP	Sorting residue; MPW	Pyrolysis Gasification Hydropyrolysis Depolymerization	unclear	Syngas, diesel Syngas Diesel, syngas BHET	MR, INC
[117,118]	2021	WP, PP, Cr2Gr	MPW	Pyrolysis	Industry	Naphtha	MR, INC, CK
[119]	2020	WP	Polymers (PET, PS, PO)	Pyrolysis Depolymerization	Modelling	Crude oil, liquid fuels Olefins, styrene, chem. intermediates	MR, INC, CK
[120]	2020	WP, PP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Industry	unclear	INC, LF
[121]	2020	PP	RDF (MSW)	Gasification	Modelling	Olefins	INC
[122]	2020	WP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Literature	Naphtha, LPG	INC
[123]	2021	WP	MR plastic fractions	Pyrolysis/depolymerization	Industry	Naphtha, slack wax, styrene	MR
[124,125]	2021	WP, PP	PE	Depolymerization	Modelling	Olefins, benzene	INC, LF
[126]	2021	WP	Recycling residue	Pyrolysis / depolymerization	Experimental	Naphtha, cracker gas	MR
[127]	2021	WP	Polymers	Pyrolysis Gasification	Modelling	Paraffins, diesel Syngas	MR, INC

WP – waste perspective, PP – product perspective, Cr2Gr – Cradle-to-Grave, MPW – mixed plastic waste, MSW – municipal solid waste, RDF – refuse derived fuel, FT – Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, INC – thermal treatment, MR – material recycling, LF – landfilling, CK – cement kiln

Table 4: Overview of LCA investigations on CR technologies (Part 2)

Source	Year	Scope	Waste fraction	Process	Process data source	Main product substitution	Reference waste treatment
[128]	2021	WP	MSW	Gasification	Modelling	Liquid fuels	INC, LF
[129]	2021	WP	HDPE	Pyrolysis	Experimental, modelling	Olefins, aromatics, naphtha, fuels	
[38]	2021	WP	RDF (MSW)	Gasification	Literature	Olefins	INC
[130]	2021	WP, PP	MPW	Pyrolysis	Unclear	Polyolefins	INC
[131]	2021	WP	PET	Depolymerization	Industry	PET	LF, INC, MR
[132]	2022	WP	RDF (MSW)	Gasification	Literature	Olefins	INC
[133]	2022	WP	RDF	Depolymerization	Industry	Olefins, aromatics	INC
[134]	2022	PP	RDF	Gasification	Modelling	Methanol	
[135]	2022	WP	MPW Polymers	Pyrolysis Solvent-based purification.	Modelling	Crude oil Polymers	LF, INC, MR
[80]	2022	Integrated system	RDF	Pyrolysis Gasification	Modelling	Naphtha, methanol Methanol, olefins, ammonia	INC

WP – waste perspective, PP – product perspective, Cr2Gr – Cradle-to-Grave, MPW – mixed plastic waste, MSW – municipal solid waste, RDF – refuse derived fuel, FT – Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, INC – thermal treatment, MR – material recycling, LF – landfilling, CK – cement kiln

4.2. TEA

4.2.1. TEA Phases

Techno-economic analysis (TEA) is an essential component of the overall project evaluation and implementation as it provides commercial and market-oriented insights into whether a technology investment leads to a monetary return, how big this return is, and when it will be realized [136]. With such insights, TEA supports decision processes regarding the investment and deployment of commercial or novel emerging technologies by providing regulatory, industrial, or public decision makers with valuable information about the preconditions to economic success [137]. Additionally, if applied according to standardized principles, TEA can support “meta assessments” to comparatively assess competing technologies or analyze impacts of specific framework conditions on individual technologies.

TEA and LCA generally have the same theoretical background, follow the same logical structure and include partly identical phases of implementation such as a detailed goal and scope definition or the collection of reliable inventory data [137]. However, no official guidelines are available to facilitate the application of TEA to CR. Hence, this report draws, inter alia, on Buchner et al. [137], Zimmermann et al. [138] and Brennan [136] to develop a

structured and standardized assessment framework in five phases to determine relevant economic aspects for its application for CR technologies:

Phase 1 – Technology characterization: Individual process characteristics are specified and the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is identified.

Phase 2 – Goal and scope definition: Important preconditions for the assessment including study aims, geographical scope and functional unit are analyzed and defined.

Phase 3 – Indicator selection: The TEA indicators as measures to economic success are selected considering the TRL and the central study aims. Additionally, methods for TEA indicator calculation are described and all relevant mathematical equations are reported.

Phase 4 – Inventory development: The market and process inventory data are collected and/or generated using, for instance, sophisticated process modelling techniques.

Phase 5 – Indicator calculation, adjustment and interpretation: The indicators are calculated, aggregated, adjusted, and tested for their sensitivity to the basic TEA assumptions in order to interpret them with regard to the central study questions.

Additional – Reporting: The precise documentation and reporting of all analysis steps is an important moderator of the TEA process to ensure result validity and facilitate an efficient communication to study recipients.

4.2.2. Overview of TEA Studies for CR Technologies

Table 5 and Table 6 provide an overview of TEA investigations in the CR context.

Table 5: Overview of TEA investigations on CR technologies (Part 1)

Source	Year	Waste fraction	CR Technology	Data sources		Main product substitution	Reference waste treatment
				Process inventory	Market inventory		
[141]	2022	LWP waste	Gasification	Modelling	Literature (CRP)	Olefins	TT and MBT
[38]	2021	rMSW	Gasification	Modelling	Literature (CRP)	Olefins	TT and MBT
[142]	2021	PET	Depolymerization	Modelling	Literature (CRP)	TA	NBT, but conventional TA production
[124]	2021	PE	Depolymerization	Modelling	Literature (CRP)	Olefins, benzene	TT and landfilling
[143]	2021	MSW	Gasification	Experimental	Literature (CRP)	Electricity/hydrogen	NBT

CRP – Conventional reference products, CR – Chemical recycling, ED – Energy demand, LWP – Lightweight packaging waste, MBT – Mechanical-biological treatment, MF – Mass flows, MSW – Municipal solid waste, NBT – No benchmark technology, PE – Polyethylene, PET – Polyethylene terephthalate, TA – Terephthalic acid TT – Thermal treatment

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Table 6: Overview of TEA investigations on CR technologies (Part 2)

Source	Year	Waste fraction	CR Technology	Data sources		Main product substitution	Reference waste treatment
				Process inventory	Process inventory		
[144]	2021	LWP waste	Gasification	Modelling	Literature (CRP)	Hydrogen	NBT
[145]	2021	MSW	Pyrolysis	Experimental and modelling	Literature (CRP)	Pyrolysis oil	NBT
[126]	2021	LWP waste	Pyrolysis/depolymerization	Literature	Literature, quality losses considered	Virgin plastics	Mechanical recycling
[146]	2020	LWP waste	Pyrolysis	Industry	Literature (CRP)	Naphtha	NBT
[147]	2020	Plastic waste	Pyrolysis	Modelling	Modelling	Olefins	NBT
[148]	2018	Plastic waste	Pyrolysis	Modelling	Modelling	Pyrolysis oil	NBT
[149]	2016	PET	Depolymerization	Experimental	Literature (CRP)	Polyester	NBT
[150]	2011	Tire waste	Pyrolysis	Experimental	Literature (CRP)	Pyrolysis oil	NBT
[151]	1998	Plastic waste	Pyrolysis	Literature	Literature (CRP)	Pyrolysis oil	NBT

CRP – Conventional reference products, CR – Chemical recycling, ED – Energy demand, LWP – Lightweight packaging waste, MBT – Mechanical-biological treatment, MF – Mass flows, MSW – Municipal solid waste, NBT – No benchmark technology, PE – Polyethylene, PET – Polyethylene terephthalate, TA – Terephthalic acid TT – Thermal treatment

While technological maturity can provide a reliable compass for the application of TEA to complex chemical processes for industrial deployment [137][138], it can be challenging to determine. ***A widely applied concept for technological maturity classification is the Technology Readiness Level i.e. TRL [137].***

General Levels of Technology Readiness [138,139]

- Level 1 *“Idea”*: The possible fields of application for a technology to solve specific technical, economic, or environmental problems are analyzed and identified.
- Level 2 *“Concept”*: A comprehensive technological concept is developed and compared with the extant patents in the field.
- Level 3 *“Proof of Concept”*: The first laboratory experiments are conducted to prove the basic functionality of the concept (e.g. testing of chemical processes in a laboratory environment).
- Level 4 *“Preliminary Process Development”*: The scale-up from laboratory experiments to pilot plant applications is started with, inter alia, the reproduction of the technological concept in preliminary computerized models.
- Level 5 *“Detailed Process Development”*: Complex process simulation models integrated with mass/energy balance data obtained from the previous laboratory experiments are developed to generate theoretical inventories (e.g. supply needs) of a pilot-scale facility.
- Level 6 *“Pilot Trials”*: A pilot scale plant is constructed, tested and further developed.
- Level 7 *“Demonstration & Full-Scale Engineering”*: A demonstration plant is constructed, inter alia, to test technical components for full-scale facilities.
- Level 8 *“Construction and Start-Up”*: A full-scale plant is constructed and harmonized with the organizational structure by integrating the recycling products in the existing supply chains.
- Level 9 *“Continuous Operation”*: The full-scale plant operates reliably at its full capacity after testing a variety of expected operation conditions and potential operational problems.
- Level 9+ *“Further Technology Development”*: Following the proof of commercial applicability, a large-scale technology diffusion in the industry comes with further technology development.

Solis and Silveira [140] identified the TRL of eight different concepts of CR. This provides a helpful guide to support the identification of additional cases.

5. Recommendations for LCA of chemical recycling

In the following sections, LCA application aspects which are of particular relevance and importance for the assessment of CR technologies will be discussed. General methodological guidelines are discussed in Section 4.1.1.

5.1. Assessment scope

The life cycle of any product can generally be divided in four phases: feedstock supply, production, utilization and disposal. The product life cycle phases and varying scopes that can be covered by an LCA are visualized in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Product life cycle phases and life cycle assessment scopes

For CR processes, both *cradle-to-gate* (often referred to as “product perspective”) and *end-of-life* scopes (“waste perspective”) are frequently applied due to the multifunctionality of CR as both waste treatment and chemical production processes. Variations in considered processes can lead to significant differences in assessment results.

To increase the comparability of LCA for different CR technologies and also with conventional production and waste treatment routes, the scope for evaluation is recommended to involve **both the end-of-life and cradle-to-gate scope.**

Figure 21 illustrates the assessment scopes in both perspectives, including the possible definitions of functional units, the conventional reference und the respective possible scopes for system expansion.

Figure 21: Illustration of waste and product perspective

Both perspectives include the same process steps. Depending on the investigated CR process, the functional unit will defer. In the waste perspective, the primary/normative functional unit is defined by the quantity and type of waste treated, while the product system is expanded to include the corresponding chemical product as a secondary functional unit. In contrast, under the product perspective, the functional unit is defined by the produced chemical quantity and expanded to include the corresponding waste amount.

Uniform life cycle stages can be excluded in comparative assessments. Additive system expansion is preferable as it is compatible with the Product Environmental Footprint (i.e. PEF) guidelines and avoids negative impact assessment results [152]. A combined application of the *cradle-to-gate* with the *end-of-life* scopes – as illustrated with the integrated reference system presented in Section 3 – is recommended as it can increase the comparability of LCA not only between different CR technologies, but also with conventional chemical production and waste treatment routes.

5.2. Specification of waste type and composition

For LCA in the CR context, ***the specification of the addressed waste fraction is critical for identification of applicable conversion technologies and a conventional reference treatment, the definition of the functional unit, allocation of background processes and subsequent quantification of the application potential.*** The required depth of waste specification depends on the intended conversion technologies. ***Criteria for waste specification*** is recommended to include:

- ***Material and fuel composition (heating value, elementary composition, non-plastic waste, plastic type, additive contamination);***
- ***Waste origin (waste source, primary/secondary waste, pretreatment).***

5.3. Product quality

Similar to the waste specification, ***the specification of the addressed chemical products is of essential relevance for assessing CR technologies.*** Possible products and required product qualities for different chemical recycling pathways have been addressed in Section 3.2.

Generally, it is preferential to apply life cycle inventories that enable the ***production of chemical intermediates at qualities that enable direct integration in value chains without quality-induced adjustments or restrictions*** (e.g. naphtha according to steam cracker specifications, methanol according to chemical grade specification). If this is not possible or realistic, the inventory scope is recommended to be ***extended to include the subsequent conversion technology to quantitatively consider effects of diverging intermediate quality*** (e.g. the effect of lower naphtha quality on the steam cracking process performance). Quantitative application limits should also be considered. At the least, the substitution factor of conventional intermediate production needs to be subjected to sensitivity and uncertainty analysis if a factual discussion/determination cannot be conducted.

5.4. Technology level & time horizon considerations

Conventionally, LCA is applied to evaluate impacts of mature and established technologies with known process characteristics – also known as retrospective LCA. Nevertheless, the deployment of LCA for emerging or developing technologies (refer to Section 4.2 for a quantification of technology development levels via Technology Readiness Level) – as in the case of CR technologies – can be helpful to evaluate future/potential environmental impacts to support the evaluation of promising technologies and identify focus points for further

development. This concept is considered as prospective LCA (also anticipatory or ex-ante LCA) [139,153,154].

For prospective LCA, process data from lower development stages is thus applied. Main issues that need to be addressed include **general data availability, compatibility, projected scaling of technologies at lower development stages and integration of uncertainty** [153,155]:

- **Data availability** – Process data availability for validation and inventory modelling is generally worst at high TRL before commercialization, since costs for implementation increase from experimental work to pilot and demonstration facilities [153]. Different methods for inventory upscaling have been proposed depending on the TRL of the addressed technology [139,156]. These include process simulation, manual calculations and application of reaction stoichiometry.
- **Compatibility** – Compatibility refers to both foreground and background processes. In comparative assessments, applied processes inventories should reflect similar development stages. Background processes (e.g. for energy supply) should reflect the expected implementation time frame of the developed technology [157].
- **Projected scaling of technologies** – The applied temporal scope of the assessment should be adapted to the expected development and implementation time frames. Three-time horizons for the foreground system (including the technology in focus) and the background system are meaningful namely current situation, situation when the technology is mature for market implementation, and situation when the technology is fully developed. In addition to temporal scope, the applied spatial scope should also be defined.
 - The **temporal scope** for the assessment of CR technologies should be defined with two objectives in mind. As CR technologies are still developing, the development trajectory should be considered when defining the reference year. Energy supply can be a significant influence on the assessment of CR, especially if the avoidance of waste incineration with energy recovery is considered. Energy generation in the EU is subject to dynamic developments. Therefore, the addressed energy supply should be matched with the reference year and the respective expected energy mix. Furthermore, it should be subjected to a sensitivity analysis when determined to be impactful.
 - For the definition of the **spatial scope**, a differentiation between general (conceptual) and specific (application) assessments should be made. Most

reviewed assessments are conceptual, focusing on a generalized application without a specific application case. As conditions can vary significantly within the EU, the framework should be focused on a defined nation with respective assessment conditions (especially for energy supply and waste composition and treatment). The defined reference system should be applied to determine the reference waste treatment process. Assessment conditions can deviate if a specific application case is defined with respect to local conditions (i.e. waste supply, infrastructural conditions).

- **Uncertainty** – Consideration of uncertainty is a matter of both foreground (i.e. CR process characteristics) and background processes (e.g. relevant energy supply mix for implementation). Methods to incorporate uncertainty in LCA are sensitivity analysis (single parameter variation), scenario analysis (variation of parameter sets) and Monte Carlo analysis (stochastic simultaneous parameter variation with probability distribution) [153,158].

5.5. Inventory modelling consistency

Maintaining consistency in inventory modelling is essential to derive realistic and applicable results from LCA and to prevent false conclusions. Due to the generalized and interdisciplinary approaches in LCA, detailed balancing and technological aspects are often insufficiently considered. These however can have significant impacts on the assessment results. Applied process inventories for CR should therefore be checked and maintained plausible during initial inventory balancing as well as during variation of process parameters for sensitivity and uncertainty analysis. Critical parameters to be checked include elementary balance (especially carbon) as well as energy and enthalpy balances. Their consistency can be monitored via measures such as Sankey diagrams for energy and carbon flows over the CR pathway.

5.6. Lack of primary data

Note that in the CR context, consistency in inventory modelling is challenged by a lack of primary data for CR technologies and/or a lack of validation for collected/reported data from CR technology providers. To address the issue of plausibility of collected primary data, an estimated check of mass/element/energy balances for major input and output streams is recommended. For conversion into uniform inventory datasets to enable comparative evaluations between different CR pathways, datasets obtained — whereby missing primary datasets can be complemented with transparent secondary datasets — should be complete

and consistent over the entire value chain. To address the problem of a lack of consistent applicable datasets for integration, adaptable complimentary baseline dataset models can be developed via process modelling/balancing and/or validated on literature data or provided datasets. The identification of critical criteria for applied waste feedstock as well as primary CR products for integration into the chemical production value chain will support the adaptation of baseline model (if possible) or the identification of required additional treatment steps.

5.7. Interpretation and reporting specification

General requirements for LCA interpretation and reporting are described in diverse documents and guidelines for LCA [159–162]. However, in the CR context, ongoing developments in the foreground system (i.e. further development in emerging CR technologies) as well as background system (i.e. dynamic changes in the energy supply) challenge the interpretation of the validity of LCA results. To address this, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses should include **the impacts of the performance of developing CR technologies on various levels** in addition to the impacts of a dynamic/changing energy production system (refer to *projected scaling of technologies* and *uncertainty* above).

Another significant challenge is posed by the conflict between transparency on inventory generation and balancing validity versus confidentiality of proprietary information. Maintaining inventory consistency and addressing the lack of a well-grounded and/or validated data basis for the assessment is thus essential to increase confidence in the accuracy and validity of the LCA results (refer to *inventory modelling consistency* above). The following measures are recommended to address this issue:

- **Graphical visualizations:** By application of non-reproducible visualizations of key balancing elements (e.g. Sankey diagrams of carbon and enthalpy flows), the consistency of inventory balancing can be substantiated without revealing quantitative process characteristics
- **Inventory checklists:** Inventory check lists are proposed (see Section 7) which summarize key aspects that need to be considered during inventory balancing for different CR processes. For practitioners, they can be applied as a measure to ensure that key aspects have been considered. For recipients, confirmation of consideration of these aspects will increase confidence in its validity, as proving false statements regarding to balancing aspects forms a higher hurdle compared to just ignoring or neglecting aspects that might impact results in an undesired way.

To prevent misuse and unsupported claims, as well as to identify mistakes or provide suggestions for more justifiable assumptions to improve the quality and robustness of the LCA study, ISO standards require the performance of an external critical review in instances where the LCA study is intended for public disclosure and used for a comparative assertion [9,163,164]. In the CR context, it is recommended to include **one reviewer with a background in chemical engineering** in the appointed critical review committee such that he/she can review the validity of the applied process balances for ensuring inventory modelling consistency.

6. Recommendations for TEA of chemical recycling

The current applications of TEA for CR technologies exhibit substantial ambiguity in methodological choices and reporting standards (see Section 4.2.2). Specifically, the application of varying numbers and types of indicators generated according to differing methodological principles have led to diverse conclusions and recommendations in the chemical recycling literature. This lack of comparability is further compounded by the significant heterogeneity in the reporting focus and structure of extant analyses, which poses additional barriers for decision-makers in tracing and interpreting the study results. Thus, **the implementation of specialized and standardized principles to TEA is urgently required in the chemical recycling literature, to ensure informative and robust support for comparative evaluation and decision processes.**

However, as no ISO-framework nor methodological guidelines are available for direct application and/or transfer to TEA in the chemical recycling context, this report draws on available TEA literature for related technologies to generate recommendations for TEA guidelines to conduct structured, comprehensive, and standardized economic assessments for CR technologies. Specifically, the five phases of TEA introduced in Section 4.2.1 are adapted for application to the evaluation of CR technologies (see Figure 22).

Techno-economic assessment for chemical recycling

Figure 22: Five phases of TEA for chemical recycling technologies based on Zimmermann et al. [138] and Buchner et al. [137]

6.1. Phase 1 – Technology characterization

In this phase, the **individual process characteristics including the required equipment, applicable waste feedstocks and/or required pretreatment steps** for a chemical recycling technology/concept are specified. Additionally, the **technology readiness level (TRL)** is

assessed from 1 “Idea” to 9 “Continuous operation” (see Section 4.2). Corresponding results provide a reliable compass for the execution of the subsequent TEA phases as they indicate which study aims are reasonable, what TEA methods are suitable, and how the required inventory data can be generated [137].

6.2. Phase 2 – Goal and scope definition

In the goal and scope definition phase, the central TEA characteristics and conditions are defined. These include [137,138]:

- study aims
- intended audience
- geographical scope
- functional unit
- temporal scope
- system boundaries
- benchmark processes

Definition of the study aims: *The study aims indicate the purpose of a TEA assessment and point to the decisions that will be based on it* [137]. They can represent e.g. decisions relating to initiating and/or continuing R&D activities for a specific chemical recycling technology, investments into chemical recycling infrastructures such as pilot, demonstration and industrial-scale plants, or process optimizations for existing chemical recycling plants via improvement of specific plant components. Table 7 provides an overview of exemplary study aims for the different TRL based on Zimmermann et al. [138] and Buchner et al. [137]. Typically, study aims at lower TRL focus on the initiation of basic R&D activities. In contrast, the decision support for investments in commercial plants can represent the central study motivation at highly TRL levels. The illustrated scheme can also be applied to check whether defined study aims are realistic or need to be adjusted.

Table 7: TEA indicator and method selection based on TRL [137,138]

TRL	TRL specific study aims	Primarily intended audience
1-3	Identify chances for the application of a chemical recycling technology; assess options for the further technology development; support the decisions on investments into the construction of a pilot plant	e.g. funding agencies and academics
4-6	Support decisions on investments regarding the construction of a demonstration plant; compare the chemical recycling technology with alternative technologies on the market (conventional processing routes)	e.g. academic and industry representatives
6-9	Support decisions on investments into the construction of a full-scale commercial plant; assess certain options for technology development in form of process optimizations	e.g. industry representatives and general public

Definition of the intended audience: *The identification of the intended TEA audience has relevant implications for the reporting of assessment results [138].* The audience may include academics, industrial representatives, the public, or a selection of these groups. A clear delimitation of the intended audience can be complex as the interest of the individual groups depends on various factors such as the (market) maturity of the technology. Table 7 above provides examples of potential audience for a TEA of a certain chemical recycling technology at particular TRL levels.

Setting of the geographical scope: The geographical scope reflects the region, country, city or area that provides the geographical background for the assessment [69]. Not only is it relevant for the availability of the data and resources for all subsequent assessment steps [137], it significantly impacts specific components of the required/applied inventory data such as prices for supplies or labor. Hence, it is **highly important to set and describe the geographical scope in detail as it may limit the transferability of TEA results to other geographical contexts.**

Definition of the functional unit: The functional unit indicates the assessment's evaluation focus e.g. "chemical recycling of X tonnes of waste per year with composition and chemical characteristics as defined by X". **A clear definition of the functional unit will facilitate comparisons between different studies on individual CR technologies [69].** Additionally, it has implications for important assessment parameters such as capacity planning (see Section 6.4). To determine the functional unit, e.g. the available waste feedstock in a defined geographical region can provide orientation. First, all waste feedstocks – with respects to their applicability to the chemical recycling technology under investigation – in the region defined as the geographical assessment scope (see above) are identified. Then, production volumes for each potential feedstock are determined, aggregated and defined as the functional unit. Specifically, waste production volumes for individual waste feedstocks can be estimated based on national and/or European statistics (e.g. [165] and [166]). Furthermore, expert interviews can also provide good estimates on available waste feedstocks for a specific region and/or case [167].

Setting of the temporal scope: The temporal scope provides **information on the time period that the TEA primarily addresses and is assumed to produce valid results for** [69]. It depends on the temporal validity of applied data which will be affected by the technology developments and improvements.

System boundary definition: A clear delineation of the system boundaries is a general requirement for TEA of CR technologies as it helps to understand **which process steps are included or excluded in the assessment.** The inclusion or exclusion of specific process steps has significant impacts on required supplies or investment costs for a chemical recycling

plant (e.g. treatment of wastewater from chemical recycling processes on-site vs. by external provider). **Visualization using block flow diagrams, process flow diagrams, or piping and installation diagrams can be useful to communicate the defined system boundaries [137,138].** Such diagrams can also **guide technical and economic data collection for the TEA inventory development.**

Benchmark system: A benchmark system is defined as the **production process/system that is currently primarily applied or the best available technique to provide the same service/product as the chemical recycling technology in focus** [138]. Having a benchmark system helps to better assess economic benefits/drawbacks of a chemical recycling technology against business-as-usual. It furthermore improves the validity of results as mistakes/inaccuracies in applied assumptions/data that affect both the chemical recycling technology and the benchmark system technology will not be relevant.

6.3. Phase 3 – Indicator selection

To enable comparative evaluations, standardization in the selection and application of TEA indicators is highly important. Relevant indicators/methods include:

- Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) [168]
- Relative gross profit [137]
- Relative profit [137]
- Static profit [137]
- Net present value [169]
- Dynamic payback period [170]
- Levelized costs of carbon abatement [171]

The maturity of a chemical technology (see TRL in Section 4.2) – usually reflecting available data – can serve as a reliable compass for indicator selection [137,138]. Table 8 summarizes TEA indicators and corresponding calculation methods for each TRL based on Buchner et al. [137] and Zimmermann et al. [138]. Individual methods/indicators for each TRL are then explained in more detail below.

Table 8: Process inventory requirements for individual TEA methods based on Buchner et al. [137] and Zimmerman et al. [138]. CAPEX: Capital expenditures. OPEX: Operational expenditures. TEA: Techno-economic analysis

TRL	Development stage	Indicators	Methods	Required inventory data
1-2	Early or mid research stages	Qualitative or semi-quantitative indicators based on expert interviews	Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) [1]	Market inventory data Expert assessments
2	Mid research stage	Basic quantitative indicators based on material/energy balances	Relative gross profit [2]	Market inventory data Mass balance from stoichiometry Energy balance from reaction enthalpy
3	Late research stage	Quantitative indicators that include additional cost position such as capital expenditure or operating labor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relative profit [2] - Specific profit [2] 	Market inventory data Mass balance from experiments Energy balance from simple thermodynamic calculations CAPEX per estimation method OPEX
4	Early process development stage	Solid static quantitative indicators that provide information about the total profit of a project e.g. in a given year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Static profit [2] - Static payback period [2] - Static Return on Investment ROI [2] 	Detailed market inventory data Mass/energy balance from experiments CAPEX from estimation method OPEX
5-6	Mid or late process development stages	Sophisticated quantitative indicators that include the time value of money/time dependence of cash flows using interest rates. Additionally, integrated indicators that combine TEA data with, example given, environmental data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Net present value [8] - Dynamic payback period [11] - Levelized costs of carbon abatement [12] - Dynamic Return on Investment ROI [2] - Internal rate of return IRR [8] 	Detailed market inventory data (including price forecasts) Mass/energy balance from experiments CAPEX from transformation method OPEX
7-8	Deployment stage	Extended quantitative indicators based on a detailed computerized view on the process itself and systemic framework conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Net present value [8] - Dynamic payback period [11] - Levelized costs of carbon abatement [12] - Economic simulations [2] 	Detailed market inventory data (including price forecasts) Mass/energy balance from plant operations and simulations CAPEX from transformation method OPEX Scenario parameter data
9	Improvement stage	Actual profitability calculations based on solid data obtained from an industry-scale plant	Cost checks and profit calculations	Accounting data from plant operation Detailed market inventory data (including price forecasts)

Multi-criteria decision analysis: As comprehensive cost data and accurate mass/energy balances that are required for sophisticated profitability assessments are typically lacking for technologies at the **TRL 1**, easy-to-apply methods with reduced data requirements should be implemented. ***Multi-criteria decision analysis is a simple method to determine whether a chemical recycling technology is more advantageous or disadvantageous compared to a benchmark technology using scoring and weighting of different economic criteria*** [168]. It includes three steps:

- ***Step 1:*** Relevant criteria such as feedstock availability/gate fees or recycling product prices are carefully selected and weighted in their importance.
- ***Step 2:*** Each criterion is quantified using market research and/or expert interviews for each technology under consideration.
- ***Step 3:*** An aggregated score is calculated based on criteria values and weightings as illustrated in Equation 1.

$$TS = \sum_{crit=1}^n Score_{crit} Weight_{crit} \quad (1)$$

with

$crit$... Economic criterion [-]

n ... Number of criteria [-]

$Score_{crit}$... Criterion score [-]

TS ... Total score for a technology [-]

$Weight_{crit}$... Criterion weighting [-]

As a result, the technology with the best aggregated score is most favorable with regards to the considered economic criteria. For chemical recycling, a technology that achieves a higher score compared to the conventional or best available technique (e.g. waste incineration) might be worth further investigation or investment.

Relative gross profit: To enable ***more quantitative insights into a chemical recycling technology, a basic understanding of inputs and outputs for feedstocks, supplies, products, and energy is required.*** With TRL 2, ***mass and energy balances applicable to basic quantitative profitability assessments/comparisons*** can be obtained from the stoichiometry and reaction enthalpy of the chemical recycling process [137]. A corresponding ***normalized measure for profitability comparisons of chemical recycling with benchmark technologies is provided by the relative gross profit.*** Specifically, amounts of products, feedstocks, supplies, and required energy are multiplied by corresponding market prices to arrive at individual cash flows. Based Buchner et al. [137], these cashflows are processed using Equation 2 to obtain normalized values for the profitability of a chemical recycling process and benchmark processes for basic comparisons. Note that the relative gross profit can only provide a basic measure for the economic efficiency of a process as other costs such

as capital expenditures are not yet included in the calculation. Inaccuracies resulting from this simplification increase with the expected investment gap between the chemical recycling process and the selected benchmark processes.

$$RGP = \frac{CF_{rev} - (CF_{feed} + CF_{sup} + CF_{en})}{CF_{feed} + CF_{sup} + CF_{en}} \quad (2)$$

with

CF_{en} ... Cash flow "Energy" [€]

CF_{feed} ... Cash flow "Feedstock" [€]

CF_{rev} ... Cash flow "Revenues" [€]

CF_{sup} ... Cash flow "Supplies" [€]

RGP ... Relative gross profit [€]

Relative profit: Based on Buchner et al. [137], the **relative profit**, illustrated with Equation 3, represents an **extension of the relative gross profit**. It **includes detailed operational and capital expenditure cash flows** to provide more sophisticated and reliable measures for the economic efficiency of a chemical recycling process and selected benchmark processes by including additional cost components. Note that the relative profit still represents a dimensionless measure that does not provide any information about the total profit that may be obtained with a certain chemical recycling technology.

$$RP = \frac{CF_{rev} - \left(CF_{opex} + \frac{FCI}{tCap} \right)}{CF_{opex} + \frac{FCI}{tCap}} \quad (3)$$

with

Cap ... Capacity [t]

CF_{opex} ... Cash flow "Operational expenditures" [€]

CF_{rev} ... Cash flow "Revenues" [€]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

RP ... Relative profit [€]

t ... Investment period [a]

Static profit: Absolute measures such as the **static profit require detailed knowledge/data about the (regional) market environment in which a chemical recycling technology will be implemented**. Specifically, **the market potential data** – e.g. feedstock volumes or recycling product market volumes typically obtainable after detailed regional market research in TRL 4 – **facilitates the estimations about the current and future feedstock processing volumes that will support, inter alia, the capacity planning for a chemical recycling plant** (with overcapacities in view of potentially rising feedstock volumes) [137]. By integrating data about the market potential of a chemical recycling technology, the static profit can be assessed using Equation 4 [137]. Note that for static profitability assessments, average values for cash

flows in the investment period are assumed and the time value of money (i.e. changes in cash flows over the investment period due to inflation) is neglected. Inaccuracies associated with these simplifications might disqualify the static profit in supporting investment decisions (e.g. in pilot scale plants).

$$SP = t V \left(CF_{rev} - \left(CF_{opex} + \frac{FCI}{tV} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

with

CF_{opex} ... Cash flow “Operational expenditures” [€]

CF_{rev} ... Cash flow “Revenues” [€]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

SP ... Static profit [€]

t ... Investment period [a]

V ... Feedstock acquisition / product sales volume [t]

Net present value: Dynamic methods such as the net present value are used to support investment decisions about pilot plants at TRLs 5 and 6. Such methods consider periods of the investment lifetime – for instance years – individually [138]. Based on Peters et al.[172] the net present value is defined as the sum of the total present value of all discounted cash flows over the entire life of an investment reduced by the fixed capital investment (FCI) in the investment base year as illustrated in Equation 5. ***The net present value method requires a solid understanding of not only the cash flows expected today but along the entire investment period.*** Additionally, ***an interest rate is introduced to discount future cash flows*** [137]. A discount rate of 15% has been suggested for new technologies such as innovative CR technologies [146]. Result of the net present value calculation is a valid measure of the expected worth of an investment discounted to the current year. Thus, if the net present value is positive, an investment is assumed to be profitable. In contrast, the investment might cause financial losses if the net present value is negative.

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^t \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k}}{(1+i)^n} - FCI \quad (5)$$

with

$CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

i ... Discount rate [%]

k ... Cashflow index [-]

NPV ... Net present value [€]

t ... Investment period [a]

Dynamic payback period: The *dynamic payback period is applied at TRLs 5 and 6 and represents the time period required to recover the initial investment in an chemical recycling plant considering the time value of money* (see Equation 6) [170]. Note that the dynamic payback period has always integer values, as cash flows in accounting are generally assumed to occur at the end of a year. Results from the dynamic payback period calculation are a valid measure of the expected project practicability for a chemical recycling plant. Specifically, it is assumed that an investment generally is practicable for a company if the payback period is short. In contrast, investment practicability is reduced for long payback periods.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{DPP} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k}}{(1+i)^n} - FCI = 0 \quad (6)$$

with

$CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]

DPP ... Dynamic payback period [a]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

i ... Discount rate [%]

k ... Cashflow index [-]

Levelized cost of carbon abatement: As investment decisions are increasingly becoming multi-criteria decisions to address not only economic but also environmental concerns, integrated indicators that consider different assessment dimensions simultaneously are utilized more often. At **TRLs 5 or 6, environmental assessment (e.g. of carbon footprint) could thus be carried out in parallel to economic assessments** to assess the *impact of a chemical recycling technology on global decarbonization efforts* [173]. **An integrated indicator that combines profitability with carbon emissions is the levelized costs of carbon emission abatement** as suggested by Friedman et al. [171]. Specifically, the levelized costs of carbon abatement reflect an investment on the basis of euros per tonne of reduced CO₂eq. as presented in Equation 7 [171]. In this regard, CO₂eq. reductions refer to a reference process which represents the currently primarily applied or the best available technique to provide the same service/product as the chemical recycling technology in focus. For calculation, these savings divide the annual cost surpluses compared to a reference technology over the entire life of the investment to arrive at specific costs to reduce a single tonne of CO₂eq.

$$LCCA = \sum_{n=1}^t \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k} - CFR_{n,k}}{CA_n} \quad (7)$$

with

$CA_{n,k}$... Annual carbon emission abatement [t]

$CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]

$CFR_{n,k}$... Annual reference cashflow [€]

k ... Cashflow index [-]

$LCCA$... Levelized cost of carbon abatement [€/t]

t ... Period of plant operation [a]

6.4. Phase 4 – Inventory development

The TEA inventory includes all the data on the economic and technical parameters as well as assumptions required to calculate the selected TEA indicators including required equipment, material and product flows, transport as well as corresponding prices [138]. As illustrated in Figure 23, inventory data can be categorized as process inventory and market inventory data.

- **Process inventory data:** This inventory includes qualitative and quantitative insights into the process in the form of expert opinions, mass or energy balance data, plant design data, or data to include additional operational expenditures such as labor or administration costs.
- **Market inventory data:** This inventory includes data on the market environment a chemical recycling technology is introduced to. For instance, it includes hourly rates for labor or trade values for chemical recycling products such as hydrogen, synthesis gas, monomers, oligomers, or higher hydrocarbons.

Figure 23: Structure of the TEA inventory

As indicated in Table 8, individual levels of the technology readiness and the corresponding profitability methods require one or more inventory data categories. Specifically, **qualitative process insights are relevant at TRL 1, mass/energy balances at TRLs 2 to 8, and capital expenditures as additional operational expenditures (i.e. not directly mass/energy flow related operational expenditures) at TRLs 3 to 8**. In the following three sections, the individual categories and corresponding data acquisition methods are presented and discussed.

6.4.1. Process inventory data

Detailed analyses of process economics are required to conduct TEA at different TRLs. The process inventory includes data on the chemical recycling process itself such as:

- qualitative insights (based on expert opinions),
- detailed mass/energy balances and associated costs,
- plant design specifics (e.g. required equipment and targeted capacity)
- additional operational information such as labor requirements

Qualitative insights: *At low levels of technology readiness, reliable data to develop detailed mass/energy balances is not available as the necessary calculations, simulations, and experiments are not yet conducted.* Hence, *qualitative interviews with experts for the chemical recycling technology under consideration can deliver valuable insights and data about the potential pros and cons of the technology use.* For example, process engineering experts can facilitate a basic understanding about the robustness of a chemical process to feedstock heterogeneity to evaluate the usability for specific cases or to identify pretreatment and sorting processes that may be required.

Mass/energy balances and associated costs: *Mass/energy balances provide a detailed list of all relevant inputs and output of a process, and of all corresponding quantities.* Inputs include feedstock needs in addition to energy and supply needs, while outputs include products of the chemical recycling process.

- **Feedstock demand** – represents the quantitative input of the waste feedstock
- **Energy/supply demand** – represents the quantitative input of energy such as external heat and electricity or process supplies such as oxygen or activated carbon
- **Product output** – represents the quantitative output of primary (i.e. recycling product) and secondary (i.e. other by-products or process residues) recycling products

A simple way to obtain corresponding data that can be applied at **low TRLs** is to derive them from the **stoichiometry and reaction enthalpy of the individual chemical reactions that are involved in a chemical recycling process** [137]. However, at **higher TRLs**, such theoretical balances should be replaced, adapted, or extended by **results and insights obtained from process modelling and experiments conducted in the laboratory or in larger scale plants**. Additionally, before applying mass/energy balances for TEA, a “sanitary check” by experts for underlying mass and energy balances to ensure that these are plausible from the perspective of physical laws is recommended [138].

Plant design specifics: The plant design specifics refer to the selection/configuration of the individual plant components (i.e. reactors vessels, pipes, etc.) and a capacity planning for the entire plant as the first step to determine capital expenditures. While the plant component requirements are typically specified in the technology characterization phase (see Section 6.1), the capacity of the entire plant can be derived from the theoretical or practical use case as described in goal and scope section (see Section 6.2).

Mass/energy balances required for TEA are often identical to corresponding balances for LCAs. Thus, if a TEA study is conducted subsequent to an LCA study for a certain technology, life cycle inventory data can be derived directly from the LCA study. Specifically, material/energy flows for the CR process can be drawn from the study if they provide the required levels of quality and detail to address TEA goals as defined in the goal and scope section (see Section 6.2).

Additional operational information: Following Brennan [136] and Peters et al. [172], additional operational information is required to assess additional operational expenditures to feedstock or energy/supply costs. Specifically, additional operational expenditures include manufacturing costs which are directly associated with the processing of a waste feedstock (e.g. operating labor costs), as well as non-manufacturing costs (e.g. administration costs) which are indirectly associated with feedstock processing. The central cost elements of the manufacturing and the non-manufacturing operational expenditures based on Peters et al. [172] are presented in Table 9 and discussed in more detail below.

Table 9: Additional components of operational expenditure based on [136], [172], and [167]. FCI: Fixed capital investment

Cost type	Cost subtype	Cost	Approach
Manufacturing operational expenditures	Variable production costs	Operating labor costs	Estimation/transformation approach
		Operating supervision costs	15% of operating labor costs
		Maintenance and repair costs	6% of FCI
		Operating supplies	15% of maintenance and repair costs
	Fixed costs	Local property tax	2% of the FCI
		Insurances	1% of the FCI
Nonmanufacturing operational expenditures	Plant overhead costs	Safety and protection costs, medical costs, restaurant costs, ...	50% of operating labor and operating supervision cost total
		Administration costs	25% of operating labor

- **Manufacturing operational expenditures:**

- **Operating labor costs** – includes wages paid to plant operation personnel based on the total required employee hours for a chemical recycling plant [169]. Corresponding employee hours can be determined using an estimation or a transformation approach.

Per estimation approach, flowsheets and technical drawings are applied that contain information about the process equipment of a plant. Based on data for typical labor requirements for plant equipment (e.g. provided by Peters et al. [172]), total required labor for a plant can then be estimated.

Using a transformation approach, labor requirements are estimated based on experiences made with similar processes and plants. Specifically, labor requirements for a new plant are related to requirements of a previously constructed plant based on the capacity ratio of both plants. Additionally, this ratio is adjusted per exponential power factor often assumed between 0.2 and 0.25 for process facilities to account for economies of scale in labor requirements [172]. Note that more detailed information about labor requirement estimation based on a transformation approach including individual power factors for different types of workers are provided by Brennan [136].

After total labor requirements are determined – either per estimation or transformation approach – representative wage rates for chemical plant workers can be drawn from the market inventory (see Section 6.4.2 below) to arrive at total (annual) operating labor costs for a chemical recycling plant.

- **Operating supervision costs** – represent expenditures that are associated with the supervision and clerical assistance for operating work [172]. For chemical plants, Peters et al. [172] suggest to assume operating supervision costs at 15 percent of operating labor costs as these cost types are typically closely connected.
- **Maintenance and repair costs** – include costs for planned and unplanned repairs of plant equipment or buildings [136]. For chemical plants, maintenance and repair costs at around 6 percent of the fixed capital investment i.e. FCI (see Table 9) can be assumed [136,172].

- **Operating supplies costs** – include expenditures for consumables such as lubricants, charts or test chemicals that cannot be considered process supplies. Annual costs can be assumed at 15 percent of maintenance and repair costs [172].
- **Laboratory services, royalties, and patents** – represent additional costs that can be included as variable production expenditures [172]. However, whether these costs are relevant for an individual chemical recycling plant depends on external factors such as the planned capacity or TRL. Detailed elaboration to such additional cost positions are provided by Brennan [136] and Peters et al. [172].
- **Insurance costs** – depend on the chemical recycling process type and the amount of available protection facilities at a chemical site [172]. A typical percentage for annual insurance costs that is assumed for chemical plants is 1 percent of the FCI.
- **Local property taxes** – are specific to a region where the chemical recycling plant is constructed. Based on Peters et al. [172], 2 percent of the FCI are suggested as a reasonable value for preliminary assessments.
- **Plant overhead costs** – represent costs that are only indirectly related to chemical recycling activities at a chemical plant site such as safety and protection services, medical services, and food services for employees [172]. As these services are closely connected to labor that is required for chemical plant operation, it is recommended to assume plant overhead costs at 50 percent of the operating labor costs and operating supervision costs total [167].
- **Non-manufacturing operational expenditures**
 - **Administration costs** – include nonmanufacturing expenditures that are incurred at the plant site for higher-level organizational tasks such as management, public relations, finance, and corporate planning by management personnel [136]. Corresponding costs are recommended to be estimated at 25 percent of operating labor costs [172].
 - **Additional non-manufacturing operational expenditures** – These can include product distribution costs, research and development costs, and selling expenses as further discussed by Brennan [136] or Peters et al. [172].

6.4.2. Market inventory data

The market inventory contains explicit information about the economic framework, i.e. the market a chemical recycling technology is introduced to. Specifically, it provides information on, inter alia:

- Gate fees for chemical recycling feedstocks
- Process supply prices
- Product prices
- Plant component/infrastructure prices
- Labor prices

Gate fees for chemical recycling feedstocks: Key market parameters such as obtainable gate fees for waste feedstocks (i.e. compensation for waste treatment paid by waste producers to waste treatment service providers) are highly relevant for the estimation of the profitability of chemical recycling. Table 10 provides data on regional gate fees for the central municipal solid waste fractions in different European countries. Negative gate fees indicate that a certain waste feedstock has a positive trade value on the market (e.g. pure plastic waste streams such as polyethylene or polypropylene from packaging waste are being sold as secondary feedstock for plastic production on the market [32]). Additional data on regional gate fees for individual waste fractions can be obtained e.g. via expert interviews. For chemical recycling, it could also be relevant to determine whether waste producers are willing to pay a higher gate fee if waste is chemically recycled instead of being used e.g. for energy recovery in waste incineration plants. Corresponding surcharge factors can be estimated using interviews with waste producers and with experts.

Table 10: Regional gate fees for individual waste feedstock fractions. LWP: Lightweight packaging. MSW: Municipal solid waste. PE: Polyethylene. PET: Polyethylene terephthalate. PP: Polypropylene. PS: Polystyrene. rMSW: Residual municipal solid waste. All values rounded to two significant digits

Waste fraction	Region	Gate fees*	Source
Compounds	Germany	0	[32]
Hazardous waste	Belgium	100 to 1500	[174]
	Denmark	100 to 1500	[174]
	France	50 to 1500	[174]
	Germany	50 to 1500	[174]
	Italy	100 to 1000	[174]
	Netherlands	50 to 5000	[174]
	Sweden	50 to 2500	[174]
Large plastic containers	Germany	-240 to -190	[174]
LWP waste	Belgium	180	[175]
	France	160	[176]
	Germany	150	[32]
	Italy	82	[177]
Mixed plastics	Germany	- 30 to 0	[32]
MSW	Belgium	57	[174]
	Denmark	40 to 70	[174]
	Finland	50 to 100	[174]
	France	50 to 120	[174]
	Germany	100 to 350	[174]
	Italy	70 to 120	[174]
	Netherlands	90 to 180	[174]
	Sweden	38 to 67	[174]
	United Kingdom	20 to 40	[174]
Paper/cardboard	Germany	-60 to -30	[32]
PET bottles	Germany	-120 to -180	[32]
Plastic foil	Germany	-150 to -50	[32]
rMSW (MSW reduced by source separated fractions)	Germany	140	[178]
LWP sorting residues	Germany	-90 to -50	[32]
Standard packaging polymers (PP, PE, PS, PET)	Germany	-120 to -100	[32]

*negative values indicate positive trade values, in explanation, prices to pay for waste as feedstock

Process supply prices: Besides waste feedstocks, **chemical recycling processes require supplies such as electricity, heat, and/or catalysts.** To arrive at reliable **estimates for current product prices for supplies, national or international databases that report trade volumes and values for commodities** can be applied. Data on energy prices in European member countries is continuously being published by the European Commission in energy reports [179]. A data source that can support estimates on chemical process supplies such as fuels and/or chemicals is the PRODCOM database that provides production quantities and trade values for commodities reported by European members [180]. Corresponding data for

most commodities/services as reported by close to 200 countries and areas globally is presented by the UN Comtrade Database [181]. Additional relevant databases are reported by Zimmermann et al. [138] and listed in Table 11. Note that if there is no economic data for commodities available, qualitative market research approaches such as expert interviews can be conducted to obtain the required information. Note that catalysts and solvents can represent a significant expenditure in chemical (recycling) processes and should therefore be considered in detail [182].

Table 11: Data sources for chemical recycling process commodities/products [138]

Source	Cost type	Region	Access
Alibaba	Industry price data	China	Open
AlphaSights	Expert interviews	Worldwide	Restricted
Argus Media	Industry price data, market studies	Worldwide and country-specific	Restricted
ICIS	Industry price data, market studies	Worldwide and country-specific	Restricted
IHS Markit	Industry price data, market studies	Worldwide and country-specific	Restricted
Platts	Industry price data, market studies	Worldwide and country-specific	Restricted
PRODCOM database	Trade volumes and values for goods	EU members	Open
UN Comtrade Database	Trade volumes and values for goods	Worldwide and country-specific	Open

Product prices: Besides economic data on feedstocks and process supplies, **key market parameters for chemical recycling products are highly relevant to estimate the profitability of chemical recycling** [138]. Market research is conducted to determine key market parameters for chemical recycling products such as base chemicals including hydrogen, synthesis gas, monomers, oligomers, or higher hydrocarbons. Based on Buchner et al. [137], the identification of key market parameters includes 3 steps:

- **Step 1: Benchmark identification** – identifies all competing products or substitution options for a chemical recycling product (or by-product) as benchmark products [137]. Typically, these benchmark products are conventional chemical products produced from fossil resources (e.g. benchmark product for olefins produced from waste gasification and subsequent syntheses is represented by olefins produced from fossil carbon resources such as crude oil [167]). Note that if no applicable benchmark products exist for a chemical recycling product, qualitative market research such as customer interviews can be conducted.

- **Step 2: Benchmark price analysis** – analyzes sales prices for each benchmark product as key economic parameters. To arrive at good estimates for current market product prices for chemicals, national or international databases can be applied (see Table 11). For example, data from the PRODCOM database or the UN Comtrade Database can be used to estimate benchmark product prices [180,181].
- **Step 3: Market trade value calculation** – sales prices for benchmark products are taken as a basis to determine corresponding values for chemical recycling products. Specifically, benchmark product parameters are adjusted based on information – obtained using market research or expert interviews – about customer needs and willingness to pay a price premium (e.g. +20%) for chemical recycling products. If market research is not feasible, a conservative approach is to assume that chemical recycling products and conventional products have the same trade value.

Plant component/infrastructure prices: To determine prices for individual chemical recycling plant equipment items (e.g. reactors, heat exchangers, filters, pumps, and conveyor belts), published information obtained from operating companies, governmental reports, or textbooks can be used. Other data sources for chemical equipment are Couper [183], Sinnott & Towler [169], Turton et al. [184], and Peters et al. [172]. To determine prices for entire chemical recycling plants (i.e. capital expenditures), estimation methods and transformation methods can be applied [136,137].

- **Estimation methods** – The quantification of capital expenditures for CR technologies is typically challenging as most CR technologies are at low stages of technology development which limits data availability. While data from industry-scale chemical recycling facilities may serve as a basis for orientation, this is often not available due to confidentiality reasons or because corresponding plants are not realized yet. As such, estimation methods can provide an effective solution as they model capital expenditures from the bottom up. Specifically, they aggregate costs to purchase and install all required plant components (i.e. FCI) with land costs, start-up expenses, working capital and contingency costs as described below [136,137,172].
 - **Fixed capital investment (FCI)** – this is typically calculated in detail while the rest of the capital expenditure components (i.e. land costs, start-up expenses, etc.) are estimated per factors applied to the FCI. Specifically, FCI for chemical plants can be further divided into inside battery limits (IBL) and outside battery limits (OBL) investments, whereas the battery limits represent a (imaginary) geographic boundary around the chemical recycling plant [137]. Thus, IBL reflects all investments necessary to build the plants core process facilities

including direct costs of physical components (e.g. reactor vessels, piping and electric installations) and indirect costs for services (e.g. engineering, supervision, construction, legal and contractor fees). On the other hand, OBL reflects all investments that link the plant to the outside world (e.g. roads, railroads) and external service plants (e.g. power plant, fire protection) [137].

Depending on the TRL, IBL investments are estimated based on flowsheets/ technical drawings at low levels of technology maturity or based on realized reference plants at higher levels of technology maturity. Either way, the foundation for further assessment steps is a list of required equipment. Costs for individual equipment items are drawn from the market inventory (see Section 6.4.2). The sum of all purchased equipment costs is usually referred to as plant equipment costs. To arrive at IBL investments, process plant equipment costs are typically related to a 'Lang' factor that reflects additional costs to plant realization such as site preparations, foundations, piping, and electrics. For most chemical process plants, a factor in the range of 3 to 4 is applied to account for such additional costs [136]. OBL investments range typically between 5 to 100 percent of the IBL capital. Note that the final amount of OBL investments can depend on various factors including type of process technology, site location, project implementation, and the use of OBL facilities by additional processes at site [136].

- **Land costs** – these are sometimes excluded from capital expenditure assessments as investments in land are potentially recoverable at the end of a project life due to the assumption that land usually retains its value [136]. However, if land costs are included in the assessment, it is reasonable to distinguish between greenfield sites and brownfield sites. Greenfield reflects the construction of a plant at a new site, while brownfield reflects the construction at an existing site. For brownfield developments, constraints arising from already existing infrastructures and operations could lead to additional costs [136] while opportunity for integration in and co-utilization of existing infrastructures and operations could lead to lower costs.
- **Start-up expenses** – represent costs that are required to put a plant in operation mode including costs for checking, purging, testing and proving of a plant [136]. According to Buchner et al. [136], start-up costs for process plants fall between 1 to 10 percent of the FCI of a plant, with higher costs typically arising for newly developed plants due to lack of experience with plant processing.

- **Working capital** – this is defined as capital required to initiate and maintain the operation of a chemical recycling plant [136]. Specifically, working capital can refer to money invested into supplies that are kept in stock or cash that is kept in hand for monthly payments of operating labor [172]. To estimate working capital for chemical plants, Peters et al. [172] suggest 10 to 20 percent of total capital expenditures as a reasonable assumption. Note that a more sophisticated approach to working capital estimation is discussed by Brennan [136].
- **Contingency** – this represents capital that is required for addressing unexpected problems or events such as unforeseen expenses due to errors in planning, transportation accidents, and strikes [172]. According to Peters et al. [172], experience shows that a contingency factor of 5 to 15 percent of the FCI is reasonable for the construction of chemical plants.

Transformation approach: For CR technologies at higher stages of technology development (e.g. at levels greater than 6, a pilot plant may already have been built), capital expenditure data for existing plants may be available that can be adapted to other framework conditions in view of temporal price deviations, plant size adjustments, and location characteristics [137]. To transform capital expenditure data from existing plants, Peters et al. [172] suggest a “power factor to capacity ratio approach”. As illustrated in Equation 8, capital expenditure data from a previously constructed plant is related to a new plant based on the capacity ratio of both plants. Additionally, this ratio is adjusted per exponential power factor to account for the effect of economies of scale, often assumed between 0.6 and 0.7 for process facilities [137,172]. Additionally, capital expenditures are adjusted by a cost index ratio to account for temporal price changes in plant equipment. A corresponding index is represented by the chemical engineering plant cost index (CEPCI) that is reported annually in the magazine Chemical Engineering [185]. It is important to note that the identical approach can be applied to individual equipment items of a plant to e.g. generate data for the estimation method.

Additional approaches to estimation and transformation methods for capital expenditure estimations are discussed by Buchner et al. [137], Brennan [136], and Peters et al. [172].

$$CAPEX = CAPEX_{rp} \left(\frac{cap}{cap_{rp}} \right)^{\kappa^{inv}} \left(\frac{pindex}{pindex_{ry}} \right) \quad (8)$$

with

cap ... Capacity [t]

CAPEX ... Capital expenditures [€]

κ^{inv} ... Scaling power factor [-]

pindex ... Price index in year of construction [-]

rp ... Reference plant [-]

ry ... Reference year [-]

Labor prices: *To determine additional operational expenditures, data of employee wages are required.* For instance, data of employee wages in the chemical sector across European member countries are publicly available in European statistics provided by EUROSTAT [186].

6.5. Phase 5 – Indicator calculation, adjustment and interpretation

According to Zimmermann et al. [138] and Buchner et al. [137], TEA indicators represent calculated values that

- provide information about absolute or relative – i.e. in comparison to other projects/investments – monetary gains or losses of an investment, and
- reveal if, how, how much, and when a certain investment is profitable.

The calculation, adjustment, and interpretation of indicators in the final phase of TEA provides an indication whether study goals as set in the goal and scope definition phase are achievable (see Section 6.2). Specifically, in this step, the indicators are calculated based on methods elaborated in the Section 6.3 and based on an inventory dataset as developed in Section 6.4. To improve the comparability of indicator results for different chemical recycling processes or to aggregate results from different indicators, normalization and weighting approaches can be applied. Finally, sensitivity and scenario analyses enable additional indicator interpretation.

Normalization and weighting of indicator results: The normalization of indicator results (see [138]) can represent an effective tool to facilitate meaningful and reliable comparisons between different assessments for chemical recycling. Per application of categorical scaling and rescaling, the comparability of study results is increased as small dissonances in applied datasets are resolved:

- **Categorical scaling** – assigning the value of an indicator to an ordinal scale from one to ten
- **Rescaling** – relating the value of an indicator to a specific value such as the highest absolute value measured on a scale from one to ten using division [138].

With either approach, normalization can increase the comparability of assessment results among different studies to support meta assessments and to provide valuable insights into how a certain chemical recycling technology performs economically compared to other chemical or conventional treatment technologies.

Weighted multi-indicator assessments: With such assessments, multiple relevant economic characteristics of a chemical recycling technology can be assessed simultaneously. These indicators can address the profitability of an investment, the required period for investment amortization, or the value of an investment with regards to positive environmental impacts such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction. Using a weighting approach, the complexity of potentially contradictory implications originating from individual indicator results – which could possibly lead to confusion and indecisions by decision-makers – is reduced. Analog to individual criteria in multi-criteria decision analyses as mentioned in Section 6.3, (normalized) indicators are weighted in their relevance to investment decisions. Subsequently, an aggregated indicator can be derived by adding up all weighted indicator values for a chemical recycling technology [138].

Sensitivity and scenario analyses: TEAs are deterministic in their nature, whereby uncertainties in supply prices or investments are typically neglected [146]. However, uncertainties in assumptions or errors in applied datasets can significantly impact assessment outcomes, eventually leading to suboptimal investment decisions for CR technologies.

Sensitivity analysis is an effective tool to assess the impacts of uncertainties and errors in assessment assumptions using alteration of central assessment parameters. Results of a sensitivity analysis help to assess the risk involved in making an investment decision about a chemical recycling technology with regard to specific assessment data and assumptions. To conduct a sensitivity analysis, various parameters including

- total capital expenditures,
- supply costs, and
- sales prices of recycling product

are altered assuming a percentual range of error for each factor [169]. In contrast, a scenario analysis changes multiple parameter at a time to generate complex and realistic scenarios for chemical recycling applications e.g. in different countries or under different policy conditions. Such insights are highly important to understand the compatibility of CR technologies with

future waste treatment and chemical production systems. The scenario analysis for chemical processes is further described by Buchner et al. [137].

6.6. Reporting

In addition to the execution of TEA assessments based on the recommendations presented above, a meticulous documentation and reporting of study characteristics is highly important to ensure that knowledge can be derived from the TEA results to support decision processes. ***A comprehensive, transparent, accurate, and structured reporting that is tailored to the needs of the primarily intended audience avoids ambiguity and misinterpretation for the recipient and allows the traceability and reproducibility of study results*** [138].

Content: Reporting is a process that covers all phases of TEAs. For each phase, the most relevant background information, data, assumptions and/or results must be documented and reported to ensure the comprehensiveness of result generation.

TEA assessment reports can be structured according to TEA phases, starting with

- Section 1 – a basic technology description that provides basic information about the chemical recycling technology under consideration including feedstock requirements or recycling products;
- Section 2 – goals and scopes of the assessment analogous to e.g. life-cycle assessments;
- Section 3 – applied indicators and corresponding assessment methods;
- Section 4 – process and market inventories including a detailed description of the technical process characteristics;
- Section 5 – assessment results linked to study aims and corresponding questions raised in the goal and scope section;
- Section 6 – additional information about the assessment including authors, contributors, and reviewers complemented by their individual professional background.

A detailed checklist is presented in Section 7.6 to support the inclusion of all important content in TEA study reporting.

Readability: It is very important to align the readability of the report with the needs/capabilities of the intended audience. Zimmermann et al. [138] suggest to utilize technical terminology if study recipients possess research and development expertise e.g. funding agencies, academics, and industry representatives. However, such language should be used with caution if recipients do not have research development expertise (e.g. government representatives or the general public).

Review: To ensure a high degree of assessment/reporting quality and traceability for the reader, Zimmermann et al. [138] suggest to implement a detailed review process to TEA of chemical processes. The first step is to identify and acquire a reasonable number of reviewers with suitable professional backgrounds in TEA, process engineering, and waste treatment. Following that, the review can be conducted – similar to a peer-review processes in scientific journals – as an iterative process between the authors of the TEA report and reviewers that is completed when all reviewer concerns have been addressed. In the report, all reviewers and their individual technical backgrounds should be stated clearly such that the validity of the TEA results is traceable for study recipients.

7. Checklists

7.1. LCA Checklist for liquefaction-based chemical recycling

No.	Process Steps	Yes	No	N.A.
Feedstock & Feedstock Preparation				
1.	The waste feedstock fits the process requirements for:			
	<i>feeding (particle size and form, melting point)</i>			
	<i>composition (including PET, PVC, non-plastic contents)</i>			
2.	For pre-sorting of the waste feedstock:			
	<i>The material and enthalpy balances of pre-sorting are consistent</i>			
	<i>The demand in pre-sorting process steps, energy and utilities are considered</i>			
	<i>The treatment of rejected waste fractions is considered</i>			
3.	Energy/facility demands for the pre-conditioning (i.e. drying, shredding, melting) of feedstock are considered.			
Liquefaction Process				
4.	The supply of process utility materials necessary for continuous operation (e.g. catalyst, neutralization agent, hydrogen, feeding oil) is considered.			
5.	Material and elementary balances for the liquefaction process (including feedstock, process utilities, product oil, aquatic phase, gas, solid residue) are consistent.			
6.	The enthalpy balance of the process (including the heating values of the reactive components, products and the reaction enthalpy) is consistent.			
7.	The energy balance of the process (including feedstock preheating and external energy supply) is consistent.			
8.	External energy supply for endothermic processes is considered.			
9.	Fuel supply and emissions from combustion flue gas for fired process are considered.			
10.	For exothermic process: process temperature control/cooling is considered.			
Performance Variation				
11.	Documentation is provided of:			
	<i>the current/considered Technology Readiness Level</i>			
	<i>the demonstrated application scale/capacity</i>			
12.	Performance parameters (including oil yield, energy demand) are considered:			
	<i>for the currently demonstrated process scale</i>			
	<i>for optimal process performance that can be reasonably expected</i>			
13.	The process balances (elementary, energy, enthalpy) during performance parameter variation are maintained consistent.			
Residue Treatment				
14.	The treatment of product gas from the liquefaction process is considered.			
15.	Documentation of the intended treatment of solid residue is available.			
16.	Thermal treatment of solid residue (including associated emissions and possible energy recovery) is:			
	<i>considered</i>			
	<i>not considered. Instead, the effects of alternative treatment (e.g. application in cement kilns) on conventional process performance and application limitations are discussed. Allocation as coal substitute (i.e. only consideration of coal extraction) is avoided.</i>			
Product Oil Processing				
17.	Substitution of:			
	<i>crude oil-based side products (e.g. atmospheric residue or petcoke) is avoided</i>			
	<i>liquid fuel-associated products (e.g. crude oil, heavy fuel oil, diesel, feedstock for catalytic cracking) is avoided</i>			
18.	The substitution of a large-scale commodity chemical in the quality for direct substitution – including all processing steps – is addressed .			
19.	For substitution of steam cracking feedstock (naphtha) or BTX recovery (pygas), adjustment of critical quality criteria of naphtha (including contents of unsaturated and aromatic hydrocarbons, boiling range, hetero atoms):			
	<i>by hydroprocessing (including hydrogen demand, energy demand, yields of side products, treatment of waste gases, facility demand) is considered</i>			
	<i>Is not considered. Instead, the impacts of inferior feedstock application (production impairment, application limits) are quantitatively addressed</i>			

7.2. LCA Checklist for gasification-based chemical recycling

No.	Process Steps	Yes	No	N.A.
Feedstock & Feedstock Preparation				
1.	The waste feedstock fits the process requirements for:			
	<i>feeding (particle size and form, melting point)</i>			
2.	For pre-sorting of the waste feedstock:			
	<i>The material and enthalpy balances of pre-sorting are consistent</i>			
	<i>The demand in pre-sorting process steps, energy and utilities are considered</i>			
3.	Energy/facility demands for the pre-conditioning (i.e. drying, shredding, pelletizing, torrefaction) of feedstock are considered.			
	<i>The treatment of rejected waste fractions is considered</i>			
Gasification Process				
4.	For autothermal gasification, the oxygen supply is considered.			
5.	For allothermal gasification:			
	<i>energy supply is considered</i>			
6.	The generated product gas quantity and composition are suitable to the applied waste feedstock and gasification technology.			
	<i>For fired heating, flue gas emissions are considered</i>			
7.	Material and elementary balances for the gasification process are consistent (including feedstock, process utilities, product gas, solid residue).			
8.	The enthalpy balance of the process (heating values of the reactive components, products and the reaction enthalpy) is consistent.			
9.	The energy balance of the process (including external heat exchange) is consistent.			
10.	External energy supply for endothermic processes is considered.			
Performance Variation				
11.	Documentation is provided of:			
	<i>the current/considered Technology Readiness Level</i>			
12.	Performance parameters (including syngas yield, composition, carbon conversion) are considered:			
	<i>The demonstrated application scale/capacity</i>			
	<i>for the currently demonstrated process scale</i>			
13.	for optimal process performance that can be reasonably expected			
	The process balances (elementary, energy, enthalpy) during performance parameter variation are maintained consistent.			
Residue Treatment				
14.	A suitable treatment method for the solid residue – depending on the expected characteristics (especially carbon content, leachability) – is considered.			
Product Gas Processing				
15.	Substitution of:			
	<i>crude oil-based side products (e.g. atmospheric residue) is avoided</i>			
	<i>natural gas or fuel gas is avoided</i>			
16.	liquid fuel-associated products (e.g. crude oil, heavy fuel oil, diesel, feedstock for catalytic cracking) is avoided			
	Suitable product gas processing steps (emissions, energy balance, waste and side product production, utility demand) are balanced for:			
	<i>syngas composition adjustment</i>			
17.	<i>contaminant and acid gas removal</i>			
	<i>off-gas processing (sulfur recovery, thermal treatment)</i>			
18.	The substitution of a large-scale commodity chemical in the quality for direct substitution – including all processing steps – is addressed .			
19.	The assumed chemical synthesis characteristics (product yield and composition, energy balance, side products, utility demand) are realistic for the assumed syngas composition.			
20.	Product refining to required purity for substitution of conventional commodities is considered.			
21.	Off-gas thermal processing is considered.			
22.	For Fischer-Tropsch based naphtha production, improved steam cracking performance compared to conventional naphtha is considered.			

7.3. LCA Checklist for depolymerization-based chemical recycling

No.	Process Steps	Yes	No	N.A.
Feedstock & Feedstock Preparation				
1.	The waste feedstock fits the process requirements for:			
	<i>feeding (particle size and form, melting point)</i>			
	<i>composition (including non-target polymers, contaminant contents)</i>			
2.	For pre-sorting of the waste feedstock:			
	<i>The material and enthalpy balances of pre-sorting are consistent</i>			
	<i>The demand in pre-sorting process steps, energy and utilities are considered</i>			
	<i>The treatment of rejected waste fractions is considered</i>			
3.	Energy/facility demands for the pre-conditioning (i.e. drying, shredding, melting) of feedstock is considered.			
Depolymerization Process				
4.	The supply of process utility materials necessary for continuous operation (e.g. makeup solvent, catalyst, neutralization agent, alkaline solution) is considered.			
5.	Material and elementary balances for the depolymerization process (including feedstock, process utilities, product fraction, fuel gas, solid and liquid residue) are consistent.			
6.	The enthalpy balance of the process (including the heating values of the reactive components, products and the reaction enthalpy) is consistent.			
7.	The energy balance of the process (including feedstock preheating and external energy supply) is consistent.			
8.	External energy supply for endothermic processes is considered.			
9.	Fuel supply and emissions from combustion flue gas for fired process are considered.			
10.	For exothermic process: process temperature control/cooling is considered.			
Performance Variation				
11.	Documentation is provided of:			
	<i>the current/considered Technology Readiness Level</i>			
	<i>the demonstrated application scale/capacity</i>			
12.	Performance parameters (including oil yield, energy demand) are considered:			
	<i>for the currently demonstrated process scale</i>			
	<i>for optimal process performance that can be reasonably expected</i>			
13.	The process balances (elementary, energy, enthalpy) during performance parameter variation are maintained consistent.			
Residue Treatment				
14.	The treatment of fuel or waste gas from depolymerization or processing is considered.			
15.	Documentation of the intended treatment of solid and liquid residue is available.			
16.	Thermal treatment of solid and liquid residues (including associated emissions and possible energy recovery) is considered.			
Product Processing				
17.	Substitution of:			
	<i>fuel gases are avoided</i>			
	<i>unpurified chemical intermediates are avoided.</i>			
18.	The substitution of a large-scale commodity chemical in the quality for direct substitution – including all processing steps – is addressed.			
19.	If standardized chemical quality (including purity, contaminant contents) is not achieved directly from depolymerization, product separation and purification processes are described and considered in inventory balancing (including energy and utility demand, product yield and purity).			

7.4. LCA Checklist for solvent-based purification

No.	Process Steps	Yes	No	N.A.
Feedstock & Feedstock Preparation				
1.	The waste feedstock fits the process requirements for:			
	<i>feeding (particle size and form, melting point)</i>			
	<i>composition (including non-target polymers, contaminant contents)</i>			
2.	For pre-sorting of the waste feedstock:			
	<i>The material and enthalpy balances of pre-sorting are consistent</i>			
	<i>The demand in pre-sorting process steps, energy and utilities are considered</i>			
	<i>The treatment of rejected waste fractions is considered</i>			
3.	Energy/facility demands for the pre-conditioning (i.e. drying, shredding) of feedstock is considered.			
Solvent-Based Purification Process				
4.	The supply of process utility materials necessary for continuous operation (e.g. makeup solvent, non-solvent) is considered.			
5.	Material and elementary balances for the extraction and recovery process (including feedstock, solvent/non-solvent, target polymer and additives, residues) are consistent.			
6.	The enthalpy balance of the process (including the heating values of the reactive components, products and the reaction enthalpy) is consistent.			
7.	The energy balance of the process (including feedstock preheating and external energy supply) is consistent.			
8.	External energy supply is considered.			
Performance Variation				
9.	Documentation is provided of:			
	<i>the current/considered Technology Readiness Level</i>			
	<i>the demonstrated application scale/capacity</i>			
10.	Performance parameters (including oil yield, energy demand) are considered:			
	<i>for the currently demonstrated process scale</i>			
	<i>for optimal process performance that can be reasonably expected</i>			
11.	The process balance (elementary, energy, enthalpy) during performance parameter variation is maintained consistent.			
Residue Treatment				
12.	The treatment of waste gas is considered.			
13.	Documentation of the intended treatment of solid and liquid residues is available.			
16.	Thermal treatment of solid and liquid residues (including associated emissions and possible energy recovery) is considered.			
Product Substitution				
14.	The quality of the recovered polymer is considered in relation to the addressed primary polymer and its functionality is considered in terms of:			
	<i>heteropolymers and non-polymer residues (including solvent residues, additives, and degradation products)</i>			
	<i>polymer quality (chemical and morphological composition; mechanical and rheological properties)</i>			
15.	Quality shortcomings compared to primary polymers are addressed by application of substitution ratios and are subject of sensitivity/uncertainty analysis in reasonable boundaries.			

7.5. TEA Checklist for chemical recycling

No.	Process Steps	Yes	No	N.A.
Technology characterization				
1.	The individual process characteristics (process steps, applicable waste feedstocks and required pretreatment steps) are specified and reported.			
2.	The TRL is identified and reported.			
Goal and scope definition				
3.	The study aims are defined according to TRL and reported.			
4.	The intended audience is specified according to TRL and reported.			
5.	The geographical scope (e.g. region or country) is set and reported.			
6.	The functional unit is defined and reported.			
7.	The temporal scope (i.e. temporal validity of results) is set and reported.			
8.	The system boundary (e.g. waste water treatment included/excluded):			
	<i>is defined</i>			
	<i>is visualized per graphical scheme</i>			
9.	The benchmark system is defined .			
Indicator selection				
10.	The TEA indicators are selected based on TRL and reported.			
11.	The TEA indicator calculation methods are selected and documented.			
12.	The inventory data requirements are defined.			
Inventory development				
13.	All required process inventory data (e.g. mass/energy balances, equipment requirements) is gathered based on applied indicator(s).			
14.	All required market inventory data (e.g. feedstock gate fees, prices for equipment/supplies/products) is gathered based on applied indicator(s) and reported.			
Indicator calculation, adjustment, and interpretation				
15.	The results from multiple indicators are weighted to reduce assessment complexity.			
16.	The indicator results are normalized to facilitate comparisons between individual chemical recycling technologies and/or applications.			
17.	Sensitivity analyses are conducted to reduce uncertainties in assessment assumptions.			
18.	Scenario analyses are conducted to investigate the impact of framework conditions such as governmental regulation.			
19.	All relevant qualitative and quantitative assessment results including implications for study aims and recommendations for study recipients are reported.			
Reporting				
20.	The TEA assessment report is clearly structured (e.g. according to TEA phases).			
21.	The TEA report is understandable for the intended audience.			
22.	A review of the TEA report was conducted and documented.			

8. Case studies

The case studies presented in this chapter illustrate how identified challenges in the LCA and TEA for CR technologies could be addressed, and how the checklists presented in Section 7 could be implemented to support LCA and TEA evaluations.

The case studies include LCA and TEA for two exemplary CR technologies without reference to actual technology providers. The CR technologies address the utilization of secondary waste fractions from light weight packaging material recycling that are not further applicable as secondary feedstock via mechanical recycling. These are namely:

- Mixed plastic waste residues (MPW) for liquefaction-based chemical recycling, and
- Sorting residues (SR) for gasification-based chemical recycling.

Typical yields for conventional (i.e. status quo) and advanced mechanical recycling are shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Product fractions from mechanical recycling of light weight packaging in Germany [187]

The case studies are conducted as a prospective assessment, considering the technology readiness level before full-scale industrial implementation and the future application with shifting footprints of attributed energy (electricity and heat). As conventional reference, incineration with energy recovery is considered. The applied thermal efficiency for electricity and district heating production reflects the best available technique (BAT) level. As waste incineration is a highly mature technology, further technology development and implementation beyond BAT level is not applied. The assessments are carried out in an End-of-Life (EoL) scope, meaning that previous life cycle stages of the waste fractions are not considered (i.e. zero burden approach).

Pyrolysis technology

A catalytic, electrically driven (i.e. process heat generation by friction) process is assumed as pyrolysis technology. The process was demonstrated for the application of MPW without the necessity of prior mechanical removal of non-polyolefinic materials, and as a single-unit facility that is not in constant operation, meaning that long-term performance decline cannot be ruled out. The TRL is estimated at level 7 to 8.

The following cases are evaluated for waste pyrolysis namely:

- First implementation case: based on the demonstrated size and performance characteristics.
- Design case: includes the application of larger pyrolysis units to the size of currently demonstrated pyrolysis units [47]. Improvement of specific performance parameters are not expected from scaling.
- Reduced process performance during continuous operation for:
 - reduced oil yield from lower waste conversion, and
 - reduced thermal efficiency from a higher process temperature is required to achieve the demonstrated oil yield.

The addressed product is naphtha for steam cracker application. Subsequently, a large-scale centralized hydroprocessing unit for pyrolysis oil upgrading is considered. The technology is available commercially (e.g. PureStep™ technology by Haldor Topsoe Rewind® Mix by Axens [57,58]) and is considered at TRL 9.

Figure 25 illustrates the process steps for waste pyrolysis which is considered for the case studies.

Figure 25: Process steps for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling

Gasification technology

For gasification, a pressurized fixed-bed autothermal gasifier with steam and oxygen is assumed. The technology was demonstrated in the past at industrial scale for the application of waste, but is currently only operated in pilot scale in non-continuous operation. The TRL is currently estimated at 6 to 7.

The following cases are evaluated namely:

- First implementation case: Based on past demonstrated configuration.
- Ongoing development and scaling to industrial scale include the implementation of a secondary gasification stage to raise the gas temperature to improve the syngas composition. Technology scaling is considered in two configurations:
 - Design case: for projected optimal conditions, and
 - Reduced performance case: for suboptimal industrial implementation.

To be applicable for fixed-bed gasification, sorting residue from LWP sorting residue as feedstock requires compacting to generate a refuse-derived fuel (RDF). Methanol is considered as product from syngas utilization. Downstream processes include a quench/scrubber unit, CO shift, acid gas removal with sulfur recovery and methanol synthesis. These syngas processing technologies are commercially available with maximum technology readiness, with numerous units implemented in coal gasification (currently especially in China) and heavy oil partial oxidation facilities (e.g. in the refineries in Wesseling and Leuna in Germany).

Figure 26 illustrates the process steps for waste gasification which is considered for the case studies.

Figure 26: Process steps for gasification-based chemical recycling

The case studies aim to illustrate the impacts of varying technological performance of CR technologies on environmental and economic impacts, accounting for:

- the lack of data on process characteristics under varying conditions, and
- lack of demonstration data on the downstream processes in the specific application case, while
- maintaining material and energy consistency over the process chain.

To address the above, inventory data is generated by detailed process modelling and balancing based on validation for the first implementation cases. Similarly, inventory data for waste incineration was modelled by process simulation to maintain consistency with general modelling assumptions and consider the application of BAT level technology as well as the impact of the specific waste characteristics on incineration and energy recovery performance.

The considered assumptions and general modelling conditions are provided for:

- CR process characteristics in the respective cases (Table 12),
- composition of the applied waste fractions and the considered liquid products (Table 13 und Table 14)

general gasification and syngas processing (Table 15 and Table 16),

- pyrolysis oil hydroprocessing (Table 17),
- waste incineration (Table 18, Table 19 and Table 20).

The resulting process inventories are shown in Table 21, Table 22, Table 23 and Table 24.

Table 12: Overview of technology level cases and modelling assumptions

Pyrolysis				
Cases	First implement. case	Design case	Reduced oil yield	Reduced thermal efficiency
Waste input capacity [kt/year]	5	18	18	18
mass liquid yield	0.75	0.75	0.5	0.75
Temperature	350	350	350	450
Gasification				
Cases	First implement. case	Design case	Reduced performance case	
Waste input capacity [kt/year]	300	300	300	
specific heat loss	5%	1.50%	1.50%	
slag C content	1%	1%	4%	
dust C conversion	0%	99%	50%	
Exit temperature	750	1100	950	

Table 13: Composition of waste fuels

Waste feedstock		Sorting residue	MPW*
Proximate analysis			
Moisture	wt.-%	4.9	0.1
Fixed carbon	wt.-% (wf)	13.9	3.9
Volatiles	wt.-% (wf)	75.9	89.0
Ash	wt.-% (wf)	10.3	7.0
Sum	wt.-% (wf)	100.0	100.0
Ultimate analysis			
Ash	wt.-% (wf)	10.3	7.0
Carbon	wt.-% (wf)	52.7	75.7
Hydrogen	wt.-% (wf)	8.1	11.0
Nitrogen	wt.-% (wf)	1.0	0.3
Chlorine	wt.-% (wf)	0.7	0.9
Sulfur	wt.-% (wf)	0.2	0.2
Oxygen	wt.-% (wf)	27.0	4.7
Sum	wt.-% (wf)	100.0	100.0
Lower heating value	MJ/kg (wf)	23.1	38.0

*MPW composition: 38% PE, 35% PP, 16% PS, 2% PVC, 9% PET

Table 14: Composition of liquid flows

		Naphtha	MPW pyrolysis oil
Paraffins	wt.-%	72.7	49.5
Olefins/Naphthenes	wt.-%	21.3	35.1
Aromatics	wt.-%	6.0	15.4
Sum	wt.-%	100.0	100.0
Carbon	wt.-%	84.80	84.75
Hydrogen	wt.-%	15.17	13.42
Oxygen	wt.-%	0.00	0.14
Nitrogen	wt.-%	0.00	1.66
Chlorine	wt.-%	0.00	0.00
Sulfur	wt.-%	0.01	0.03
Sum	wt.-%	100.00	100.00
Lower heating value	MJ / kg	44.2	44.5
10 vol.-%	°C	53	130
50 vol.-%	°C	77	290
90 vol.-%	°C	138	425

Table 15: Modelling assumptions for gasification [70,188,189]

Pressure	40 bar
Oxygen purity	99.5 vol.-%
Steam-oxygen ratio	0.9 kg / m ³ (STP)
Burner fuel gas	2.6 m ³ (STP) / t feed
Flushing gas input (CO ₂)	16 m ³ (STP) / t feed
Dust formation in primary raw gas	20 g / m ³ (raw gas, STP, wf) 82 wt.-% carbon
Pelletization electricity demand	77 kWh / t feed [190]

Table 16: Modelling assumptions for syngas processing and utilization

water quench and scrubber [71,78]	
Temperature	
Quench water preheating	120 °C
Syngas after scrubber	200 °C
Maximum chloride content in water cycle	2000 ppmw
Maximum solid loading in quench water	3 wt.-%
Scrubber stage number	4
Scrubber water cycle purge	10 %
CO shift [71]	
Steam/dry gas ratio (molar)	1.5
Entry temperature HT/LT stage	280 / 180 °C
Physical absorption (Rectisol) [191]	
Methanol solvent feed temperature	- 60 °C
Columns stage number: Prewash / H ₂ S column / CO ₂ column	5 / 12 / 18
Reabsorber pressure stages	3.5 / 1.3 bar
Regenerator head temperature	30 °C
Regenerator pressure	3.0 bar
Claus process [74]	
Temperature thermal stage	1200 °C
Excess air ratio	0.33
Input temperature catalytic stages	300 / 250 / 140 °C
Sulphur recovery	99.5 %
Methanol synthesis [78,79,192,193]	
Reactor temperature	255
Reactor pressure	60
Syngas modulus	2.05
Recycle ratio	3.5
Column stage number	70 / 90
Methanol purity	99.9 wt.-%
Methanol carbon recovery	> 95 %

Table 17: Modelling assumptions for pyrolysis oil hydroprocessing

	Hydrotreater	Hydrocracker
H ₂ - feed ratio	200 m ³ /m ³ liquid	1000 m ³ /m ³ liquid
Reactor inlet temperature	320 °C	360 °C
Reactor inlet pressure	75 bar	75 bar
Sources	[194,195]	[196–198]
Pyrolysis oil product fractionation		
Stage number	25	
Bottom temperature	270 °C	
Naphtha exit temperature	180 °C	

Table 18: Modelling assumptions of the waste gas incineration process

Flue gas temperature after energy recovery	200 °C
Burner excess air ratio	1.2
Non-fuel specific emission values	[22]
Reference state	Flue gas dry, 3 vol.-% oxygen
CO	40 mg / m ³ (STP)
Particles	0.5 mg / m ³ (STP)
NO _x	100 mg / m ³ (STP)

Table 19: Applied technology configurations for BAT waste incineration [39,199]

LP turbine outlet pressure	mbar	60
Air preheating temperature (via intermediate steam extraction)	°C	150
Flue gas outlet temperature (for condensate preheating)	°C	140
Intermediate steam reheating	°C	400
HP steam pressure	bar	130
HP steam temperature	°C	440
Flue gas recirculation	%	20

Wastewater treatment and utility balancing

Wastewater treatment is balanced according to a performance indicator-based life cycle inventory model for waste water treatment in the chemical sector [205].

Calculated processing steps include nanofiltration, wet-air oxidation, mechanical-biological treatment and

sludge incineration. The WWT process configuration is adjusted depending on waste water composition to fulfil emission limits, provided in [205].

Cumulated process utilities are reported under the following assumptions:

- Produced fuel gas combustion is applied for direct heating and supply of HP and IP steam,
- excess steam is thermally integrated for electricity production,
- cooling water is applied in a closed cycle with water loss of 2 % due to evaporation [206],
- boiler feed water (BFW) is prepared by membrane separation processes with utility demands of 1.175 t fresh water and 0.66 kWh electricity per t BFW [207].

Table 20: Modelling assumptions for waste incineration process [39,200–204]

Radiation heat loss	3.0 % of LHV input
Unconverted carbon	1.5 %
Combustion fly ash formation	3000 mg / m ³ (STP)
Combustion NO _x formation (grate firing)	350 mg / m ³ (STP)
Air excess ratio	1.8
Light fuel oil input	2.5 l / t waste input
Flue gas temperature after economizer	180 °C
Isentropic efficiency of HP / LP turbine	92 % / 90 %
Plant electricity demand	4 % of LHV input
Heat export condition	5 bar saturated steam
CHP electric-thermal output ratio (σ)	0.35
Dry-gas acid gas removal with slaked lime	
Ca-(SO ₂ + HCl) ratio (molar)	2.0
Activated carbon input	5 wt.-% of lime input
DeNO _x ammonia-NO _x ratio (molar)	1.1
Emissions to air (BAT average)	mg / m ³ (STP)
Dust	3.5
HCl	4
HF	1
SO ₂	17.5
NO _x	85
CO	30
NH ₃	6
CH ₄	6.5

Table 21: Overview of balanced process utilities for process chain balancing

Utility	Lower bound	Upper bound
HP steam	90 °C; 45 bar	275 °C; 45 bar
LP steam	90 °C; 5 bar	160 °C; 5 bar
Cooling water	20 °C; 1 bar	30 °C; 1 bar
Electricity		

Process inventories

Table 22: Process inventories for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling process chain

		First implementation / Design case	Reduced oil yield case	Reduced thermal efficiency case
Input				
MPW	kg	13.33	20.00	13.33
Electricity	MJ	19.84	22.73	23.03
Caustic	kg	0.006	0.008	0.006
Sulfuric Acid	kg	0.005	0.006	0.005
Fresh Water	kg	16.37	16.24	17.89
Limestone	kg	0.07	0.10	0.07
Catalyst	kg	0.27	0.40	0.27
Hydrogen	kg	0.26	0.26	0.26
Output				
Naphtha	kg	9.17	9.17	9.17
LPG	kg	0.85	0.85	0.85
LP Steam	kg	2.88	2.12	2.88
Sulfur	kg	0.002	0.002	0.002
Residue	kg	2.99	9.48	2.99
Emission to air				
CO2 diffuse	kg	1.29	1.62	1.29
SO2	kg	2.45E-04	2.45E-04	2.45E-04
CO	kg	1.95E-04	2.11E-04	1.95E-04
Dust	kg	2.45E-06	2.65E-06	2.45E-06
NOX	kg	4.91E-04	5.31E-04	4.91E-04
Emission to water				
COD	kg	3.88E-10	3.88E-10	3.88E-10
Chloride	kg	7.73E-06	1.16E-05	7.73E-06
Sulfate	kg	1.50E-03	1.96E-03	1.50E-03
Residue				
C	wt.-%	47.78	67.28	47.78
H	wt.-%	2.42	8.22	2.42
N	wt.-%	0.39	0.26	0.39
O	wt.-%	1.80	1.73	1.80
Cl	wt.-%	4.08	1.93	4.08
S	wt.-%	1.00	0.48	1.00
A	wt.-%	42.54	20.10	42.54
Sum	wt.-%	100.00	100.00	100.00
LHV	MJ/kg	25.99	35.26	25.99

**Report process
inventory data**

 LCA-Checklists: items 7-10
 TEA-Checklist: item 14

Overcoming Challenges of LCA & TEA for Chemical Recycling

Table 23: Process inventories for gasification-based chemical recycling process chain

		First implementation case	Design case	Reduced performance case
Input				
Sorting residue	kg	10.00	10.00	10.00
Electricity	MJ	-8.85	7.51	0.94
Caustic	kg	0.08	0.09	0.08
Sulfuric Acid	kg	0.01	0.01	0.01
Fresh Water	kg	78.30	68.42	68.11
Oxygen	kg	3.48	5.74	4.49
Fuel gas	MJ	0.96	0.98	0.97
Output				
Methanol	kg	3.23	6.75	5.24
Sulfur	kg	0.02	0.02	0.02
LP Steam	kg	41.87	11.61	23.19
Bottom Ash Slag	kg	0.95	0.95	0.98
Filter residue	kg	0.35	0.07	0.28
Emission to air				
CO ₂ concentrated	kg	7.27	8.34	7.59
CO ₂ diffuse	kg	5.73	0.71	2.86
SO ₂	kg	4.10E-04	1.25E-03	1.35E-03
CO	kg	1.85E-03	2.01E-04	9.10E-04
Dust	kg	2.32E-05	2.53E-06	1.14E-05
NO _X	kg	4.63E-03	5.01E-04	2.27E-03
Emission to water				
COD	kg	2.85E-03	2.53E-03	2.15E-03
Chloride	kg	1.52E-02	2.68E-02	1.49E-02
Sulfate	kg	2.76E-03	3.61E-03	3.07E-03

Table 24: Process inventories for incineration processes

		Sorting residue	MPW	Residue (26 MJ)	Residue (35 MJ)
Input					
Waste input	kg	10	10	10	10
Activated carbon	kg	0.003	0.008	0.002	0.001
Ammonia	kg	0.020	0.033	0.026	0.035
Slaked lime	kg	0.363	0.987	0.261	0.092
Fresh water	kg	69.11	116.00	84.02	121.08
Fuel oil	kg	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.021
Output					
Electricity	MJ	37.5	64.0	46.3	66.7
LP Steam	kg	44.8	76.5	55.2	79.9
Bottom Ash / Slag	kg	0.96	0.63	1.94	0.61
Fly ash	kg	0.52	1.29	0.43	0.27
Emission to air					
NH3	kg	5.62E-04	9.08E-04	7.14E-04	9.60E-04
CO2 diffuse	kg	18.15	26.24	14.56	25.35
CO	kg	2.81E-03	4.54E-03	3.57E-03	4.80E-03
PM	kg	3.28E-04	5.29E-04	4.17E-04	5.60E-04
CH4	kg	6.09E-04	9.83E-04	7.74E-04	1.04E-03
Nox	kg	7.97E-03	1.29E-02	1.01E-02	1.36E-02
SO2	kg	1.64E-03	2.65E-03	2.08E-03	2.80E-03

Further, scaled carbon and enthalpy (based on heating value) streams for the assessed technology cases are presented to discuss the impacts that technology implementation differences will have on the overall balance. For both pyrolysis and gasification-based CR, it is shown that the carbon balance is consistent for all assessed cases over the waste processing chain. Gaps in the enthalpy balance are associated with the effective chemical reaction enthalpy of the respective conversion step and lead to an energy exchange. The form of the exchange (e.g. via cooling water, steam generation, electrical driving) is determined by the process type and conditions. Non-chemical energy exchanges (e.g. physical heating and cooling, gas compression and expansion) cannot be derived from the enthalpy balance, but are included in the inventory balancing.

For pyrolysis-based CR (see Figure 27), it is shown that the oil yield impacts the carbon and enthalpy balance significantly. Conversion losses to solid residue are not determined by the mass yield as well as the residue composition (carbon content/heating value). The pyrolysis process itself is a slightly endothermic process, while the hydroprocessing is exothermic. The impact of lowered thermal efficiency (higher necessary reaction temperature for constant oil

yield) cannot be visualized in the enthalpy balance, but will be addressed in the LCA part of the assessment.

Figure 27: Visualization of carbon and enthalpy balances for the pyrolysis-based CR cases

Gasification-based CR (see Figure 28) shows only minor difference in the carbon and enthalpy flows between the different cases up to the methanol synthesis stage, where the differences between methanol and off-gas yield become strong. The main driver of differentiation is the methane content in the produced syngas, which is not convertible to methanol in the process. Methanol carbon recovery varies significantly between 24% and 50% depending on the applied technology case. Further it is shown that all process steps in the gasification process chain are net-exothermic and do not require external energy to fulfill chemical enthalpy demands.

Figure 28: Visualization of carbon and enthalpy balances for the gasification-based CR cases

8.1. LCA

8.1.1. Reference processes

First, the processes and datasets that are applied for both CR cases are documented. These include the considered evolving footprints for electricity and heat supply, background processes and the incineration of MPW and sorting residue as the respective conventional reference.

Energy supply

For all waste treatment options ranging from pyrolysis, gasification to incineration, it is assumed that supply or demand of electricity is met by the average electricity generation mix for Germany in the respective year. The same goes for excess heat, which is generated for all technologies and which is assumed to replace district heat that is generated in the average source mix. Therefore, development projection scenarios for both electricity and district heating

supply are necessary for the assessment. Development scenario investigations on the German energy system are available in academic [208–210] and non-academic literature [211–214]. Projections of district heating development are addressed less frequently [215]. The report by BCG and Prognos [214] is applied due to its relative actuality, the consideration of German emission reduction targets and the inclusion of electricity and district heating development. Three pathways for energy system transformation are presented. The middle pathway (80% pathway) is used for this study. The reconstructed production compositions for the average electricity and heat supply are presented in Figure 29, including the calculated CO₂ footprint based on GaBi process inventories for individual energy sources.

Figure 29: Energy production composition projection and resulting CO₂ footprint for electricity (left) and district heating (right)

Background processes

Allocated products and utilities are summarized in Table 25. This includes aggregated GaBi datasets for end-of-life treatment of solid residues from incineration and gasification, direct landfilling of bottom ash and slag and advanced treatment of fly ash (including incineration, macro encapsulation, vitrification, transport and landfill). System expansion is applied for variable or non-available dataset, i.e. incineration with energy recovery for carbonaceous pyrolysis residues, oxygen supply for gasification by cryogenic air separation and catalyst supply. Oxygen supply at 99.5 vol.-% purity by cryogenic air separation is calculated with an electricity demand of 0.245 kWh/kg oxygen [216]. The applied pyrolysis catalyst is assumed to be a zeolitic material. Applicable inventories for catalyst production are not available in GaBi databases, but can be reproduced from the GREET catalyst module [217]. The generated input materials are presented in Table 26. The resulting calculated CO₂ footprint at 9.5 kg CO₂eq / kg is in reasonable alignment with the reported footprint by GREET (7.7 kg CO₂eq / kg [218]). Grimaldi et al. [219] report a lowered impact up to 1.8 kg CO₂eq / kg for the production of a zeolitic catalyst.

Table 25: Allocated background processes

Allocated products / processes	Allocation	GaBi data set / source
Main products		
Naphtha	Mass	DE: Naphtha at refinery
Methanol	Mass	DE: Methanol from natural gas
Side products		
LPG	Mass	DE: Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG)
Sulphur	Mass	DE: Sulphur (elemental) at refinery
Utilities		
Ammonia	Mass	DE: Ammonia (NH ₃) without CO ₂ recovery
Slaked lime	Mass	DE: Calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH) ₂ ; dry; slaked lime)
Heavy fuel oil	Mass	DE: Heavy fuel oil at refinery
Caustic	Mass	DE: Sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) mix (100%)
Sulfuric acid	Mass	DE: Sulfuric acid mix (96%)
Lime	Mass	DE: Lime (CaO; quicklime lumpy)
Activated carbon	Mass	DE: Activated carbon
Ash/slag end of life treatment		
Fly ash treatment	Mass	DE: Hazardous waste (statistic average) (C rich, worst case scenario incl. landfill)
Bottom ash / slag treatment	Mass	DE: Inert matter (Construction waste) on landfill

Table 26: Inventory of production of ZSM-5 catalyst [218]

Input		Input	
Toluene	0.18 kg	TPAOH	0.98 kg
Ammonia	0.84 kg	NaOH	0.05 kg
NaOH	0.2 kg	γ-Al ₂ O ₃	0.06 kg
Propane	0.88 kg	SiO ₂	0.94 kg
HCl	0.73 kg	H ₂ O	4.65 kg
Acetonitrile	0.16 kg	Heat (natural gas)	55.8 MJ
Heat (natural gas)	12.9 MJ	Electricity	0.43 MJ
Output		Output	
TPAOH	1 kg	ZSM-5 catalyst	1 kg

Waste incineration

The generation of a reference footprint for waste incineration of the two waste fractions is documented in the following. The functional unit the treatment of 1 kg of sorting residue and MPW, respectively. The addressed inventory system is illustrated in Figure 30. The results for the global warming impact (GWI) with changing reference energy year are shown in Figure 31. It is shown that the direct emissions from incineration are only specific to the applied waste composition. Benefits from energy substitution decrease with increasing renewable energy production, thus leading to an overall increase in the environmental impact of waste incineration in the future

Figure 30: Inventory system for waste incineration

Figure 31: Results for global warming impact for waste incineration

8.1.2. LCA for liquefaction-based chemical recycling

Goal and scope definition

The objective of this investigation is the evaluation of pyrolysis-based CR of MPW under the condition of varying technology development levels and developments of the energy system in Germany in an attributional LCA. Various impact categories of the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology are assessed to consider the possible occurrence of contradictory effects. Furthermore, the assessment is used to support the identification of environmental hotspots and possible focus points for further development.

The functional unit is defined as the treatment of 1 kg of MPW. A zero-burden-approach is applied, meaning that waste generation is not considered as a supply chain. Moreover, waste collection and transportation are considered uniform between all treatment options and are therefore excluded.

Life cycle inventory

The assessed inventory system is shown in Figure 32. The assessment scenario is varied in two perspectives:

- (1) between the applied pyrolysis technology level between the first implementation case/design case, the reduced oil yield case and the reduced thermal efficiency case, and
- (2) between the reference years 2025, 2035 and 2045 for electricity and district heat generation.

Figure 32: Inventory system for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling

Life cycle impact assessment

The environmental impacts of various impact categories are initially scanned to determine the environmental hotspots. Total environmental impact of the design case in 2025 is normalized according to the Environmental Footprint normalization factors and cumulated to determine the impact categories that are most significantly affected by the defined system. Please note that normalization does not weigh the different impact categories against each other in general significance, but puts the individual impact of the specific case in relation to the total category impact of the European Union divided by the total population number [220]. Normalized impacts are presented in person equivalents (PE) in Figure 33, as well as scaled results to increase visibility. It is apparent that significant impacts primarily concern global warming (GW) and resource depletion of fossil resources (FRD). Other impact categories in water scarcity (WSC), acidification (AC), eutrophication (EUT) and photochemical ozone formation (POF) show significantly lower normalized impacts. Pyrolysis-based CR shows a net improvement compared to incineration (i.e. Inc Reference) in three of the six addressed impact categories i.e. GW, FRD, WSC.

Figure 33: Normalized impact assessment results for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling (left, scaled to 1 on right)

The global warming impact (GWI) is focused on to enable a more detailed discussion on the inventory variation. Results are shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Global warming impact results for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling

- For all assessed scenarios, the net GWI is lower than the conventional treatment by incineration. The margin is observed to increase with increasing renewable energy content in the associated grid mix.
- Product naphtha credits and energy balances show a significant impact on GWI.
- Further significant impacts include solid residue treatment by incineration, hydrogen demand for oil upgrading and catalyst supply, which could be overestimated due to uncertainty in the applied data (see Section 8.1.1).
- Direct emissions from pyrolysis and pyrolysis oil upgrading (i.e. incineration of pyrolysis gas and hydrotreating off-gas), consumed utilities and co-produced LPG are of minor significance.
- It is shown that the energy efficiency of the pyrolysis process has only a minor impact on GWI. Both the design case and the reduced energy efficiency case show an insignificant influence of the associated reference energy year, partially determined by the neglecting effects of net electricity consumption and net heat supply by the system.
- For a reduced oil yield from pyrolysis, the resulting GWI is significantly higher and increases with energy system development, due to higher emissions from residue incineration with decreasing credits from generated energy.

- The impact of balances of electricity and heat are cumulated between the pyrolysis, hydroprocessing and incineration processes, and are shown in more detail in Figure 35 for the 2025 reference year.
- The demand for pyrolysis energy is the largest contributor to electricity demand and increases specifically with lower thermal efficiency. On the other hand, the pyrolysis electricity impact only slightly decreases with lowered oil yield, as the energy is mostly required for physical heating of the process which is required independently of the waste conversion rate.
- Lowered oil yield furthermore leads to a significant increase in energy production from residue incineration and a less significant decrease in excess heat supply from oil hydroprocessing.

Figure 35: Global warming impact results of energy-related aspects for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling for 2025

8.1.3. LCA for gasification-based chemical recycling

Goal and scope definition

The objective of this investigation is the evaluation of gasification-based CR of sorting residue under the condition of varying technology development levels and developments of the energy system in Germany in an attributional LCA. The functional unit is defined as the treatment of 1 kg of sorting residue. A zero-burden-approach is applied, meaning that waste generation is not considered as a supply chain. Further, waste collection and transportation are considered uniform between all treatment options and is therefore excluded.

Life cycle inventory

The assessed inventory system is shown in Figure 36. The assessment scenario is varied in two perspectives:

- (1) between the applied gasification technology level between the first implementation case, the design case and the reduced performance case, and
- (2) between the reference years 2025, 2035 and 2045 for electricity and district heat generation.

Figure 36: Inventory system for gasification-based chemical recycling

Life cycle impact assessment

Similar to the pyrolysis investigation, significant impacts primarily concern global warming (GW) and resource depletion of fossil resources (FRD). Other impact categories in water scarcity (WSC), acidification (AC), eutrophication (EUT) and photochemical ozone formation (POF) show significantly lower normalized impacts (cf. Figure 37). A positive impact compared to the incineration reference is shown for GW and FRD.

Figure 37: Normalized impact assessment results for gasification-based chemical recycling (left, scaled to 1 on right)

Figure 38 shows the global warming impact of the assessed scenarios.

Figure 38: Global warming results for gasification-based chemical recycling

- Again, all scenarios show a better GWI compared to the incineration reference, with increasing margin as the energy system develops.
- The main impacts include direct process-based CO₂ emissions from syngas conditioning (concentrated CO₂ from acid gas removal), emissions from off-gas incineration, credits for methanol substitution and cumulated impacts of the electricity and heat balance. Side products, utilities and residue treatment impacts are minor.
- For the design case at maximum syngas yield, GWI stays uniform due to neglecting effects of net electricity consumption and net heat supply by the system. With decreasing syngas yield for the reduced performance and first implementation cases, the impact of energy recovery from off-gas incineration becomes more prevalent. For high credits for heat and electricity exports, this leads to a lowered GWI compared to the design case. In these cases, GWI increases rapidly with a developing energy system.

Again, the distribution of energy-related GWI is discussed in more detail, shown in Figure 39.

- Process related electricity demand is distributed between the process steps pelletization, oxygen supply by ASU, acid gas removal and methanol synthesis.
- Process steam is required for gasification, but is generated in excess from syngas shifting and cooling, methanol synthesis and off-gas incineration.
- The overall influence of energy-related impacts is small compared to process and product impacts for high syngas yields, but becomes increasingly significant with increasing off-gas yield.

Figure 39: Global warming results of energy-related aspects for gasification-based chemical recycling for 2025

8.1.4. Product perspective

In addition to the previously applied End-of-Life (EoL) perspective, both CR technologies are assessed from a product perspective for the generated CR products. The same datasets are applied for the EoL assessment. In a product perspective, CR products are not considered by substitution of the fossil alternative. Instead, the conventional reference includes both production of the conventional fossil feedstock and the conventional treatment of the considered waste (multifunctionality). The functional unit is defined as a consistent amount chemical product and the associated waste quantity, which is determined by the CR product yield and changes with product yields in varying process configuration cases. Below, the respective inventory systems and results for GWI impact assessment are shown.

The applied system boundaries are shown in Figure 40 and Figure 41, GWI results are shown in Table 27 and Table 28. As a cumulative approach is applied, no negative impacts are calculated for individual conventional waste treatment (WT), conventional chemical production (CC) or CR individually. Major qualitative tendencies identified in the EoL assessment can also be shown in the product perspective (including favorable impact of CR compared to the conventional reference in all cases, increasing margin with further reference year, low impact of energy footprint in high-yield cases). In contrast to the EoL assessment, a favorable impact for low-efficiency gasification is not shown, due to scaling to the produced chemical quantity.

Concerning the applied framework, system expansion enables the application of the CR technology specific product footprint in relation to the conventional alternative (comparison of CR with CC+WT), but requires clear communication on the applied conventional references in waste treatment and chemical production. In contrast, a subtraction approach (comparison of CC with CR-WT) enables a relation of the alternative chemical footprint to the conventional chemical production footprint. However, the calculated chemical GWI is negative in most cases. In all of the calculated cases, the GWI of the product from CR is higher compared to the conventional chemical product if the corresponding waste treatment is not considered (comparison of CR to CC).

Figure 40: Inventory system for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling assessment in a product perspective

Table 27: GWI results for pyrolysis-based chemical recycling in a product perspective

		Design			Red. Perf. (yield)			Red. Perf. (thermal)		
		2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045
Product yield in CR	kg / kg	0.69			0.46			0.69		
Reference year		2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045
Naphtha produced	kg	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
MPW treated	kg	1.45	1.45	1.45	2.18	2.18	2.18	1.45	1.45	1.45
GWI conv. chemical (CC)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52
GWI waste treatment (WT)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.90	1.64	2.98	1.35	2.46	4.47	0.90	1.64	2.98
GWI chem. recycling (CR)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.83	0.84	0.85	1.26	1.62	2.27	0.87	0.86	0.86
CC+WT (expansion)	kg CO ₂ eq	1.42	2.16	3.50	1.87	2.98	4.99	1.42	2.16	3.50
CR-WT (subtraction)	kg CO ₂ eq	-0.07	-0.81	-2.13	-0.09	-0.84	-2.20	-0.03	-0.78	-2.12

*including impacts of associated utility demand, electricity and heat balancing (demand or substitution) and side product substitution

Figure 41: Inventory system for gasification-based chemical recycling assessment in a product perspective

Table 28: GWI results for gasification-based chemical recycling in a product perspective

Case		Design			Red. Performance			First implementation		
		2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045
Product yield in CR	kg / kg	0.68			0.52			0.32		
Reference year		2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045	2025	2035	2045
Methanol produced	kg	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Sorting residue treated	kg	1.48	1.48	1.48	1.91	1.91	1.91	3.10	3.10	3.10
GWI conv. chemical (CC)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
GWI waste treatment (WT)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.88	1.33	2.12	1.14	1.71	2.73	1.84	2.77	4.43
GWI chem. recycling (CR)	kg CO ₂ eq	1.24	1.24	1.25	1.31	1.44	1.69	1.40	1.94	2.96
CC+WT (expansion)	kg CO ₂ eq	1.81	2.25	3.05	2.06	2.63	3.66	2.77	3.69	5.36
CR-WT (subtraction)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.36	-0.08	-0.87	0.17	-0.27	-1.04	-0.45	-0.83	-1.47

*including impacts of associated utility demand, electricity and heat balancing (demand or substitution) and side product substitution

8.1.5. Interpretation and limitations

In the assessed technology and waste feedstock scope, CR is observed to be an advantageous waste treatment option for greenhouse gas reduction and conservation of fossil resources compared to incineration. For both waste pyrolysis and waste gasification, low material efficiency (meaning pyrolysis oil for the former and syngas yield for the latter) is associated with increasing impact of grid energy substitution.

For gasification, it is observed that the implementation on a lower technology level would be beneficial in the short term, but technology development would lead to a significantly improved margin compared to conventional references in the future.

For pyrolysis, high material efficiency is environmentally beneficial independent of the energy mix, but the margin increases with greener electricity footprints. Energy efficiency has a minor effect on the GWI of pyrolysis-based CR. Hence, higher process temperature is acceptable if it contributes to higher oil yields.

For both technologies, efficient heat utilization is essential for their environmental performance, especially for low material efficiency. For gasification, excess heat production is dissipated over several units in the process chain. Hence, a facility location in a centralized setting with the possibility for industrial or district heat integration is preferred. For pyrolysis, heat integration is primarily relevant for oil upgrading and residue incineration. Hence, decentralized operation of the pyrolysis process will have no significant impacts on GWI performance.

Limitations

Practically, a shift in product associated impacts would be expected in the discussed timeframe for associated products and utilities due to shifts in applied technologies and the underlying energy mix. A significant impact can be expected especially for main product commodities in methanol and naphtha. Footprint development will presumably not be generated by process efficiency improvement of reference technologies (natural gas-based methanol production and crude oil refining for naphtha are highly mature technologies), but from the shift in technology to alternative feedstocks as well as electricity-based production with an unclear pathway and significant uncertainty. Due to missing data, this effect is not considered in this assessment. Furthermore, focus points to increase robustness of the results would include more detailed sensitivity/uncertainty analysis on specific technology aspects instead of criteria grouping, and the application of a concrete application setting with focus on the available local framework.

8.2. TEA

8.2.1. TEA for liquefaction-based chemical recycling

Goal and scope definition

Assessment goal is to support decisions about investments into full-scale commercial plants in the year 2022 (i.e. assessment base year). The intended audience refers primarily to industrial representatives or the general public. The functional unit is defined as the treatment of mixed plastics waste (MPW) in a liquefaction-based CR system with a capacity of 300,000 tonnes MPW a⁻¹ consisting of multiple decentralized pyrolysis plants and a single hydroporcessing plant (see Section 8, “Pyrolysis technology”). The geographic scope is set to Germany and the temporal scope is set to 2022 to 2029 as assumptions regarding waste composition or technology efficiency are based on current knowledge. As illustrated in Figure 42, the system boundary extends from the point of MPW collection at – inter alia – materials recovery facilities for lightweight-packaging waste to treatment product distribution. As the benchmark process, MPW incineration in a modern RDF power plant is investigated.

Indicator selection

The (1) fixed capital investment, (2) net present value, (3) the dynamic payback period and 3) levelized costs of carbon abatement are selected as TEA indicators. Note that all corresponding equations are provided with the Supplementary Information (SI) to this report (See Section 11).

Liquefaction-based chemical recycling

Reference process

Figure 42: Block flow diagrams for chemical recycling per liquefaction and waste incineration. MPW: Mixed plastics waste. SB: System boundary

As illustrated in Equation 1 in the SI, a power factor applied to capacity ratio approach is utilized to calculate *fixed capital investments (FCI)* (Peters et al., 2004). Investment data for individual plant components including reference capacities are multiplied by the ratio of targeted capacity to reference capacity, raised to a power factor of 0.7 and adjusted by a cost index ratio [172]. For temporal price indexing, the Chemical Engineering Plant Costs Index (CEPCI) is applied and extrapolated to 2022 based on linear regression [185].

The *net present value (NPV)* is defined as the difference between the total present value of all cash flows and the present value of all capital investment as displayed in Equation 2 in the SI [172]. For NPV calculation, FCI in the starting year of construction is considered, i.e. 2022. Furthermore, a construction period of three years is assumed [221]. After plant commissioning in 2025, cash

flows for the following are calculated over the entire plant operating time, assumed unified at 30 years for all treatment plants [222]:

- (1) local taxes and insurances,
- (2) maintenance and repair,
- (3) supplies,
- (4) labor,
- (5) overhead costs,
- (6) administration costs,
- (7) environmental expenses,
- (8) transportation,
- (9) revenues, and
- (10) income tax.

Cash flow calculations are based on Peters et al. [172] as presented in Equations 3 to 13 in the SI.

The dynamic payback period (DPP) refers to the period required to recover the investment considering the time value of money [223]. It is calculated from FCI and discounted net annual cash flows (See SI, Equation 14). Due to the assumption of cash flows occurring at the end of each year, DPP can only have integer values.

The levelized cost of carbon abatement (LCCA) refers to an investment on the basis of euros per tonne of emissions reduced [171]. Discounted additional costs for a plant investment compared to a reference treatment process are divided by the total carbon reduction from a life cycle perspective (See Section 8.1) over the entire plant operating time (cf. SI, Equation 15). Note that waste incineration which is the standard treatment for residual waste fractions (i.e. MPW, SR from mechanical recycling facilities, ...) in Germany is defined as the reference process for LCCA calculations [224].

Required inventory data include:

- market inventory data for treatment inputs/outputs,
- mass/energy balances,
- capital expenditure data, and
- additional operational expenditure data including labor requirements and assumptions regarding tax rates or the future value discount rate.

Define inventory requirements

TEA-Checklist: item 12

Inventory development

Table 29 provides central market inventory assumptions for prices based on data provided by – inter alia – the UN Comtrade database [181]. Table 30 illustrates general economic assumptions including tax and inflation rates. Primary process inventories for all process cases and incineration as the reference case including inputs, outputs and emissions are drawn from Table 22 and Table 23. Eventually, Table 31 displays additional relevant process characteristics including capacity requirements and transportation distances. Note that 90% plant availability is assumed for all treatment plants [225,226]. Also, note that process-specific labor requirements in Table 31 are based on reported requirements for German plants.

Table 29: General economic assumptions. All values rounded to two significant digits. EI: Expert inquiry. All values rounded to two significant digits

	Price in 2022	Source
Transportation		
Transportation cost rate [€ km ⁻¹ t ⁻¹]	0.06	[227]
Gate fees		
Mixed plastic waste gate fee [€ t ⁻¹]	150	EI
Refuse-derived fuels gate fee [€ t ⁻¹]	160	[32]
Labor		
Unskilled employee hour [€ h ⁻¹]	59	[228]
Skilled employee hour [€ h ⁻¹]	75	[228]
Supplies		
Activated carbon [€ t ⁻¹]	2400	[181]
Ammonia [€ t ⁻¹]	310	[181]
Calcium carbonate [€ t ⁻¹]	100	[181]
Catalyst [€ t ⁻¹]	2600	[229]
Diesel [€ t ⁻¹]	520	[181]
Electricity (buying price) [€ kWh ⁻¹]	0.16	[230]
Fresh water [€ t ⁻¹]	1.6	[181]
Fuel oil [€ L ⁻¹]	0.59	[181]
Hydrogen [€ t ⁻¹]	2600	[181]
Sulfuric acid [€ t ⁻¹]	84	[181]
Sodium hydroxide [€ t ⁻¹]	110	[181]
Products		
Electricity (selling price) [€ kWh ⁻¹]	0.081	[231], [232]
Fe scrap [€ t ⁻¹]	170	[32]
Heat [€ kWh ⁻¹]	0.025	[233]
Liquefied petroleum gas [€ t ⁻¹]	500	[181]
Methanol [€ t ⁻¹]	500	[181]
Naphtha [€ t ⁻¹]	560	[234]
Emissions		
Bottom ash deposition charge [€ t ⁻¹]	28	[40]
CO ₂ certificate price [€ t ⁻¹]	60	[235]
Fly ash deposition charge [€ t ⁻¹]	140	EI
Pyrolysis residue treatment [€ t ⁻¹]	150	EI

Table 30: General economic assumptions for treatment cost calculation. CR: Chemical recycling. I: Incineration. LWP: Lightweight packaging. All prices assumed for year 2021. Underlying values rounded to two significant digits

	Unit	Value	Source
Administration percentage	%	25	[172]
CO ₂ certificate price inflation	%	4	[236]
Consumables percentage	%	20	[172]
Corporate income tax rate	%	15	[237]
Depreciation period (linear)	a	10	[238]
Discount rate	%	8	[222]
Insurance percentage	%	1	[172]
Labor cost inflation rate	%	2.6	[239]
Labor power factor	%	0.25	[172]
Local tax percentage	%	2	[172]
Maintenance & repair percentage (CR/I)	%	4/3	[240]
Overhead percentage	%	50	[172]
Price inflation	%	1.4	[241]
Supervision percentage	%	15	[172]

Table 31: Process characteristics. CR: Chemical recycling. FI: First implementation. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. All values rounded to two significant digits

	Liquefaction-based CR				Waste incineration
	FI case	Design case	Reduced OY	Reduced TE	
System capacity [kt a ⁻¹]	300	300	300	300	300
Pyrolysis plants [No.]	61	17	17	17	-
Process steps					
Collection	•	•	•	•	•
Delivery & storage	-	-	-	-	•
Flue gas treatment	-	-	-	-	•
Grate firing	-	-	-	-	•
Hydroprocessing	•	•	•	•	-
Metal separation	-	-	-	-	•
Prefeeding & preconditioning	•	•	•	•	-
Pyrolysis	•	•	•	•	-
Labor					
Skilled labor [TEH a ⁻¹]	5	5	5	5	14
Unskilled labor [TEH a ⁻¹]	30	30	30	30	78
Distances					
Mixed plastics transport [km t ⁻¹]	20	20	20	20	20
Pyrolysis oil transport [km t ⁻¹]	300	300	300	300	-
Pyrolysis residue transport [km t ⁻¹]	50	50	50	50	-
Bottom ash transport [km t ⁻¹]	-	-	-	-	20
Fly ash transport [km t ⁻¹]	-	-	-	-	700

Report process inventory data

TEA-Checklist: item 14

Indicator calculation, adjustment, and interpretation

Fixed capital investment

Figure 43 illustrates fixed capital investments for liquefaction-based CR and incineration as the reference. Summarized, liquefaction-based CR exhibits higher FCI compared to incineration-based treatment at 420 MEUR for the FI (First implementation) case and ~300 MEUR for the design case, the reduced oil yield (Reduced OY) case, and the reduced thermal efficiency (Reduced TE) case. For waste incineration-based treatment, FCI at 160 MEUR is heavily driven by the grate-firing unit and the flue gas treatment unit. In contrast, the pyrolysis investments are the main cost driver for liquefaction-based CR. Altogether findings point to significantly increased investments (>200%) for CR compared to incineration for a capacity of 300,000 tonnes MPW year.

Report all relevant results

TEA-Checklist: item 19

Figure 43: Fixed capital investment (FCI). CR: Chemical recycling. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. All values rounded to two significant digits

Net present value

As presented in Figure 44, liquefaction-based CR will be profitable for the design case at 41 M€ and 12 M€ in the reduced thermal efficiency case, while the first implementation case and the reduced oil yield case cause significant economic losses. Other than the design case, liquefaction-based CR will generate a lower economic return than incineration. This indicates that from an NPV perspective, liquefaction process will be a reasonable investment only under optimal conditions.

Figure 44: Net present value (NPV). CR: Chemical recycling. FI: First implementation. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. All values rounded to two significant digits

Dynamic Payback period

As presented in Figure 45, the dynamic payback period for liquefaction-based CR will be 23 years for the design case, and 29 years for the reduced thermal efficiency case. Note that DPP cannot be calculated for the first implementation case and the reduced oil yield case due to a negative net present value (i.e. investment will not be paid back in the investment period). For the incineration case, a DPP of 12 years indicates a more positive project practicability in terms of return on investment compared to chemical recycling in the form of MPW pyrolysis.

Figure 45: Dynamic payback period (DPP). CR: Chemical recycling. FI: First implementation. NA: Not applicable. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. All values rounded to two significant digits

Levelized cost of carbon abatement

Figure 46 illustrates LCCA results for liquefaction-based CR for process cases with incineration as the reference. In the design case, CR will produce a negative LCCA as it reduces CO₂eq. and is also more profitable at the same time. Note that at current prices for European Emission Allowances (> 60 € t⁻¹ CO₂eq.), an investment into liquefaction-based CR appears feasible even for the first implementation case – the least favorable scenario compared to other cases [235].

Figure 46: Levelized cost of carbon abatement (LCCA). FI: First implementation. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. All values rounded to two significant digits

Indicator aggregation

Table 32 summarizes absolute results for FCI, NPV, DPP, and LCCA for all liquefaction-based CR process cases and incineration-based treatment. Additionally, absolute results are normalized based on the most favorable value in each category indicated with a '*' and then aggregated for each treatment pathway with an individual score. Among liquefaction-based cases, it appears that the design case is most favorable scenario. Note however that incineration and liquefaction-based CR are not directly comparable as incineration has no indicator result for LCCA.

**Normalize/weight
indicator results**
TEA-Checklist: Items 15-16

Table 32: Indicator normalization and weighting. DPP: Dynamic payback period. FCI: Fixed capital investment. First implementation. LCCA: Levelized cost of carbon abatement. NPV: Net present value. OY: Oil yield. TE: Thermal efficiency. *: Most favorable value. All values rounded to two significant digits

Indicator (weighting)	Unit	FI case	Design case	Reduced OY	Reduced TE	Incineration
FCI (25%)	M€	420 (0.38)	320 (0.49)	290 (0.54)	320 (0.49)	160 (1)*
NPV (25%)	M€	-590 (-14)	41 (1)*	-280 (-6.7)	12 (0.28)	35 (0.85)
DPP (25%)	a	- (0)	23 (0.52)	- (0)	29 (0.41)	12 (1)*
LCCA (25%)	€/t CO ₂	56 (-0.014)	-0.79 (1)*	29 (-0.027)	1.8 (-0.44)	-
Score	-	-3.4	0.75	-1.5	0.19	-

Sensitivity analysis

Figure 47 illustrates results of a NPV sensitivity analysis for the design case of liquefaction-based CR. Results indicate that assumptions regarding obtainable market prices for produced naphtha and the FCI will significantly impact the profitability of corresponding investments. This suggests that profitability for CR of MPW could be significantly increased if a price premium can be achieved for “secondary” naphtha. Additionally, the high impact of FCI assumptions points to the importance in system planning including decision about site integration or systemic centralization to reduce investment costs for CR.

Figure 47: Sensitivity analysis. Design case as reference. EA: Emission allowances. NPV: Net present value. S: Skilled. US: Unskilled.

8.2.2. TEA for gasification-based chemical recycling

Goal and scope definition

Primary goals are to support decisions on investments regarding the construction of a demonstration plant and to provide quantitative data to compare gasification-based CR technology with alternative technologies on the market (i.e. conventional processing routes). The intended audience refers primarily to academics and industrial representatives. The functional unit is defined as the treatment of refuse-derived fuel (RDF) in the form of sorting residues (SR) from lightweight packaging sorting in material recovery facilities in a gasification-based CR plant with a capacity of 300,000 tonnes RDF a⁻¹ (see Section 8, “Gasification technology”). The geographic scope is Germany and the temporal scope is set to 2022 to 2029 as assumptions regarding waste composition or technology efficiency are based on current knowledge. As illustrated in Figure 48, the system boundary extends from the point of SR collection at materials recovery facilities for lightweight-packaging waste to treatment product distribution.

Define goals and scopes
TEA-Checklist: items 3-9

Gasification-based chemical recycling

Reference process

Figure 48: Block flow diagrams for chemical recycling per gasification and waste incineration. SB: System boundary. SR: Sorting residues.

Visualize system boundaries
TEA-Checklist: item 8

Indicator selection

As indicators (1) the fixed capital investment, (2) the net present value, (3) the dynamic payback period and (4) the levelized costs of carbon abatement are selected. Note that indicator calculation is conducted analog to TEA for liquefaction- based CR described in Section 8.2.1.

Select suitable indicators
TEA-Checklist: item 10

Inventory development

Relevant market inventory assumptions for prices based on data provided by – inter alia – the UN Comtrade database [181] are provided with Table 29. General economic assumptions including tax and inflation rates are presented in Table 30. Process balances are drawn from Table 22 and Table 23. Additional process characteristics are displayed Table 33. Note that 90% plant availability is assumed for all treatment plants and that process-specific labor requirements in Table 33 are based on reported requirements for German plants [225,226].

Table 33: Process characteristics. FI: First implementation. RP: Reduced performance. All values rounded to two significant digits

	FI case	Design case	RP case	Waste incineration
Ref. capacity [kt a ⁻¹]	300	300	300	300
Plant availability [%]	90	90	90	90
Process steps				
Collection	•	•	•	•
Delivery & storage	-	-	-	•
Gasification	•	•	•	-
(Flue) gas treatment	•	•	•	•
Grate firing	-	-	-	•
Metal separation	-	-	-	•
Pretreatment unit	•	•	•	-
Syngas-to-methanol synthesis	•	•	•	-
Labor				
Skilled labor [TEH a ⁻¹]	10	10	10	14
Unskilled labor [TEH a ⁻¹]	59	59	59	78
Distances				
Sorting residues transport [km t ⁻¹]	20	20	20	20
Solid residues / bottom ash transport [km t ⁻¹]	20	20	20	20
Fly ash transport [km t ⁻¹]	700	700	700	700

Report process inventory data
TEA-Checklist: item 14

Indicator calculation, adjustment, and interpretation

Fixed capital investment

Fixed capital investments for gasification-based CR and incineration-based treatment are presented in Figure 49. Gasification-based CR will exhibit significantly higher FCI compared to incineration at 380 MEUR compared to 160 MEUR. For CR, the gasification unit is the main cost driver while for incineration, FCI is heavily affected by grate-firing and flue gas treatment units. Altogether, findings point to higher FCI of about 140% higher for gasification-based CR compared to incineration-based treatment for a capacity of 300,000 tonnes sorting residues per year.

Figure 49: Fixed capital investment (FCI). CR: Chemical recycling. All values rounded to two significant digits

Net present value

Gasification-based chemical recycling will be profitable for the design case at 150 M€ return on the investment, and at 63 M€ for the reduced performance case while the first implementation case will lead to significant economic losses (see Figure 50). Note that in the design case and the reduced performance cases, gasification-based CR will generate a higher economic return compared to incineration. This indicates that from an NPV perspective,

gasification-based CR of sorting residues from lightweight packaging sorting would be feasible even under the condition of reduced technical performance.

Figure 50: Net present value (NPV). CR: Chemical recycling. FI: First implementation. All values rounded to two significant digits

Dynamic payback period

Gasification-based CR will be 15 years for the design case and 21 years for the reduced performance case as presented in Figure 51, while it cannot be calculated for the first implementation case due to a negative net present value (i.e. investment will not be paid back in the investment period). For the incineration case, DPP is 17 years. This indicates that incineration may have a higher project practicability compared to the reduced performance case for gasification-based CR. This advantage however, will not hold for the design case for gasification-based CR.

Figure 51: Dynamic payback period (DPP). CR: Chemical recycling. FI: First implementation. NA: Not applicable. All values rounded to two significant digits

Levelized cost of carbon abatement

LCCA results for CR in all process cases with incineration as the reference for costs and carbon emissions are displayed in Figure 52. For the first implementation case, observed LCCA at 20 € t⁻¹ CO₂eq. are below current prices for European Emission Allowances at 60 € t⁻¹ CO₂eq. indicating that an investment into gasification-based CR is reasonable [74]. For the design case and the reduced performance cases, negative LCCA are observed as CR in these cases is more profitable and saves carbon emission simultaneously.

Figure 52: Levelized cost of carbon abatement (LCCA). FI: First implementation. RP: Reduced performance. All values rounded to two significant digits

Indicator aggregation

Table 34 summarizes absolute results for FCI, NPV, DPP, and LCCA for all gasification-based CR process cases and incineration-based treatment. Additionally, absolute results are normalized based on the most favorable value in each category and indicated with a '*' and then transferred for each treatment pathway into an individual score. Assuming that all indicators have an equal impact, the design case is most favorable among all cases for CR. Note that incineration is not directly comparable with gasification-based CR across all indicators as the indicator value for LCCA is missing.

Table 34: Indicator normalization and weighting. DPP: Dynamic payback period. FCI: Fixed capital investment. FI: First implementation. LCCA: Levelized cost of carbon abatement. NPV: Net present value. RP: Reduced performance. *: Best value. All values rounded to two significant digits

Indicator (weighting)	Unit	FI case	Design case	RP case	Incineration
FCI (25%)	M€	380 (0.42)	380 (0.42)	380 (0.42)	160 (1)
NPV (25%)	M€	-93 (-0.61)	150 (1)	63 (0.42)	9.2 (0.061)
DPP (25%)	a	0 (0)	15 (1)	21 (0.71)	17 (0.88)
LCCA (25%)	€/t CO ₂	20 (-1.1)	-19 (1)	-7.7 (0.41)	-
Score	-	-0.32	0.86	0.49	-

Sensitivity analysis

Figure 53 illustrates results of a NPV sensitivity analysis for the design case of gasification-based CR. Results indicate that assumptions regarding obtainable market prices for produced methanol and FCI will significantly impact the profitability of corresponding investments. This indicates that gasification-based CR for sorting residues can be highly profitable if a price premium for sustainable methanol from recycled feedstock is achieved. Additionally, the impact of FCI assumptions indicates the importance of a cost-effective CR plant construction including decision about site integration or system centralization, similar to liquefaction-based CR (see Section 8.2.1).

Figure 53: Sensitivity analysis. Design case as reference. EA: Emission allowances. NPV: Net present value. S: Skilled. SR: Sorting residues. US: Unskilled. All values rounded to two significant digits

8.2.3. Interpretation of results

Results from the exemplary TEA for liquefaction-based and gasification-based CR suggest that CR can outperform waste incineration from an economic perspective under optimal process conditions. Despite higher fixed capital investments, CR plants have the potential to generate a higher economic return with project profitability as indicated by a reduced investment payback period. Additionally, results for the levelized cost of carbon abatement indicate that CR can present an attractive option for reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in the future.

Sensitivity analyses highlight the significant impact of market prices for CR products. This assessment applies a conservative approach – utilizing market prices for conventionally produced naphtha and methanol. Results suggest that should CR products be traded at increased market prices, CR may present a viable alternative to waste incineration even in conditions where process conditions are not optimal.

8.3. Background information

These assessments have been conducted by Florian Keller (Process & Chemical Engineering) and Raoul Voss (Business Administration) at the Institute of Energy Process Engineering and Chemical Engineering (IEC) at the TU Bergakademie Freiberg in Germany. Results were reviewed by Prof. Bernd Meyer and Dr. Roh Pin Lee.

9. Conclusion

This technical report aims to contribute to transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability of LCA and TEA assessments in the CR context via:

- contributing to existing general LCA and TEA methodologies and guidelines,
- highlighting methodological aspects that are not consistently followed in extant LCA and TEA studies on CR technologies,
- providing recommendations to address highlighted aspects, and
- presenting LCA and TEA checklists to support CR assessments.

To achieve the above, CR processes are mapped with a focus on:

- the intersections with conventional waste treatment and chemical production pathways (i.e. waste feedstock and product chemicals),
- identification of reference processes, and
- identification of points of emphasis for process balancing.

Based on a review of previous investigations, methodological focus points for conducting LCA and TEA studies on CR technologies are highlighted and recommendations developed. Checklists are also developed to support practitioners (and reviewers) in reviewing critical aspects in LCA and TEA application in the CR context. The developed recommendations are then demonstrated on two case studies namely pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste (i.e. liquefaction-based CR) and gasification of refuse-derived fuel (i.e. gasification-based CR).

To conclude, the authors would like to highlight that the methodological recommendations presented in this report are not intended to function as independent guidelines for the assessment of CR processes. Rather, they are meant as an addition to reference guideline documents and reference methodologies that are cited in this report, and which are valid and applicable for LCA and TEA investigations. Furthermore, note that this report does not provide an applicable methodology for benchmarking and certification of CR processes and products, nor do presented case studies provide definite conclusions regarding the sustainability and viability of different CR processes as these will vary according to the addressed CR technology and the applied application and assessment framework. Rather, the case studies are meant to demonstrate the application of the methodological focus points that have been highlighted in the report as being especially relevant and important for increasing transparency, comprehensiveness and comparability of LCA and TEA assessments in the CR context.

10. References

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11. Supplementary information

$$FCI = \sum_{pc} FCI_{pc} \left(\frac{cap}{cap_{rp}} \right)^{\kappa^{inv}} \left(\frac{pindex}{pindex_{ry}} \right) \quad (1)$$

with

cap ... Capacity [t]

cap_{rp} ... Capacity of reference plant [t]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

FCI_{pc} ... Fixed capital investment for plant component [€]

pc ... Plant component index [-]

$pindex$... Price index in year of construction [-]

$pindex_{ry}$... Price index in reference year [-]

κ^{inv} ... Scaling power factor [-]

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^t \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k}}{(1+i)^n} - FCI \quad (2)$$

with

$CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

i ... Discount rate [%]

k ... Cashflow index [-]

n ... year [a]

NPV ... Net present value [€]

t ... Investment period [a]

$$CF_1 = FCI (insur + lTax) \quad (3)$$

with

CF_1 ... Local taxes and insurances [€]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

$insur$... Insurances percentage [%]

$lTax$... Local taxes percentage [%]

$$CF_2 = FCI maint (1 + consum) \quad (4)$$

with

CF_2 ... Maintenance & repair [€]

$consum$... Consumables percentage [%]

FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]

$maint$... Maintenance & repair percentage [%]

$$CF_3 = \sum_s requi_s price_s \quad (5)$$

with

CF_3 ... Supplies [€]

$price_s$... Price for s [€/t]

$requi_s$... Total requirements s [t]

s ... Supply [-]

$$CF_4 = (sEmploy sRate + usEmploy usRate) \cdot (1 + supervis) \quad (6)$$

with

CF_4 ... Labor [€]
sEmploy ... Skilled employee hours [h]
sRate ... Hourly rate for skilled labor [€/h]
supervis ... Supervision percentage [%]
usEmploy ... Unskilled employee hours [h]
usRate ... Hourly rate for unskilled labor [€/h]

$$CF_5 = CF_4 \text{ overhd} \quad (7)$$

with

CF_4 ... Labor [€]
 CF_5 ... Overhead [€]
overhd ... Overhead percentage [%]

$$CF_6 = \frac{CF_4}{1 + supervis} \text{ admin} \quad (8)$$

with

admin ... Administration percentage [%]
 CF_4 ... Labor [€]
 CF_6 ... Administration [€]
supervis ... Supervision percentage [%]

$$CF_7 = \sum_{em} \text{outp}_{em} \text{ costs}_{em} \quad (9)$$

with

CF_7 ... Environmental expenses [€]
costs_{em} ... Price for handling/treatment of *em* [€/t]
em ... Emission/contaminant [-]
outp_{em} ... Output of *em* [t]

$$CF_8 = \sum_{str} \text{outp}_{str} \text{ dist}_{str} \text{ tRate} \quad (10)$$

with

CF_8 ... Transportation [€]
dist_{str} ... Transportation distance for *str* [km]
outp_{str} ... Output of *str* [t]
str ... Solid treatment residue [-]
tRate ... Transportation cost rate [€/t/km]

$$CF_9 = \sum_{prod} \text{outp}_{prod} \text{ price}_{prod} \quad (11)$$

with

CF_9 ... Revenues [€]
outp_{prod} ... Output of *prod* [t]
price_{prod} ... Selling price for *prod* [€/t]
prod ... Product [-]

$$tinc = \sum_{k=1}^9 CF_k - depr \quad (12)$$

$$CF_{10} = \begin{cases} tinc * itax & tinc > 0 \\ 0 & tinc \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

with

CF_k ... Annual cashflow [€]
 CF_{10} ... Income tax [€]
 $depr$... Plant depreciation [€]
 $itax$... Corporate income tax rate [%]
 k ... Cashflow index [-]
 $tinc$... Taxable income [€]

$$\sum_{n=1}^{DPP} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k}}{(1+i)^n} - FCI = 0 \quad (14)$$

with

$CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]
 DPP ... Dynamic payback period [a]
 FCI ... Fixed capital investment [€]
 i ... Discount rate [%]
 k ... Cashflow index [-]
 n ... year [a]

$$LCCA = \sum_{n=1}^t \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{10} CF_{n,k} - CFR_{n,k}}{CA_n} \quad (15)$$

with

CA_n ... Annual carbon emission abatement [t]
 $CF_{n,k}$... Annual cashflow [€]
 $CFR_{n,k}$... Annual reference cashflow [€]
 k ... Cashflow index [-]
 $LCCA$... Levelized cost of carbon abatement [€/t]
 n ... year [a]
 t ... Period of plant operation [a]